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BUILDING CAPACITY AND CAPABILITY WITH A HOSPITAL QUALITY
IMPROVEMENT TRAINING PROGRAM

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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For the degree of

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By

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ABSTRACT

Medical errors are the third leading cause of death in the US. To address medical errors and improve processes and outcomes, hospital staff needs training in quality improvement (QI) methodology. This study evaluated the Quality Academy Program (QAP), a 6-month QI training program at one 600-bed acute care tertiary safety net hospital. A quasi-experimental pretest posttest design with qualitative content analysis asked five research questions about three Waves of QAP participants ($n = 63$) using self-reported surveys. These questions asked whether evidence-based elements exist and if they were incorporated in the QAP. Additional questions asked if the QAP could build capacity in the organization and capability in hospital staff to improve patient outcomes. Thirty-nine evidence-based elements were identified in the literature. Paired samples t -tests revealed significantly improved proficiency ($p < .001$). Qualitative content analysis identified positive themes from participants in the QAP. All Waves reported post Academy confidence of “somewhat” to “very confident,” demonstrating emerging capability. No significant differences were identified between Waves using Kruskal-Wallis rank sum tests ($p = .443$). Chi-square analysis was significant ($p = .014$ and $p = .001$) for participation in QI training post Academy, demonstrating developing organizational capacity. QAP participants completed 63 projects, where 16 demonstrated improved patient outcomes at the end of the training. There remains a lack of QI expertise in the practice setting, despite implementation of the QSEN initiative and the

Institute of Medicine call to action. Organizations can develop QI training programs to meet this educational need, resulting in improved patient outcomes and reduced harm.

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BACKGROUND

For the past two decades, the Institute of Medicine (IOM)¹ has been sounding the alarm on the status of health care quality. The IOM's National Roundtable, convened in 1996, declared that health care leaders should undertake "a major effort to rethink and reengineer how we . . . try to improve the quality of care" (Chassin & Galvin, 1998, p. 1001). The IOM (1999) subsequently published *To Err is Human: Building a Safer Health System* placing medical errors as the "eighth leading cause of death" (p. 2), with an estimated 98,000 deaths per year due to errors in care. This study also alleged a disorganized health care system as a contributing factor in these errors (IOM, 1999). In 2001, the IOM released *Crossing the Quality Chasm: A New Health System for the 21st Century* identifying major gaps in the quality of care and suggesting, among other things, implementation of quality improvement (QI) training (IOM, 2001). In 2003, *Health Professions Education: A Bridge to Quality* specifically recommended training in the use of QI methods and tools (IOM, 2003). Despite these calls to action, patient harm continues to occur at an alarming rate with estimates of over 400,000 adverse events per year (James, 2013). More recently, medical errors have been identified as the third leading cause of death in the US (Makary & Daniel, 2016).

Efforts to incorporate QI training in nursing and medical schools are in progress (American Council for Graduate Medical Education, 2013; Cronenwett, Sherwood, & Gelmon, 2009). Chassin and Loeb (2013) recommend "nearly all employees should be

¹ The IOM is now the Health and Medicine Division (HMD) of the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (National Academies).

trained [in formal QI methodologies] at levels appropriate to each one's job" (p. 481).

The presumption is that training will lead to development and implementation of QI initiatives and ultimately improved patient outcomes (Adams, O'Brien, & Scruth, 2015; Shortell et al., 1995; Whippy et al., 2011).

Organizations investing in training have reported improvements in their patient outcomes including lower hospital readmission rates, decreased hospital acquired pressure ulcers, improved mobility for patients after hip surgery, improved management of sepsis, improved hand hygiene, reduced falls, and improved access to care (Daniel, Puxty, & Miles, 2016; Estrada et al., 2012; Moore & Stichler, 2015; Schilling et al., 2010; Whippy et al., 2011). Hospitals may benefit from having staff with knowledge, experience, and confidence to conduct QI projects in their clinical settings.

Training efforts are intended to build capacity and capability to lead QI initiatives, which would be expected to improve patient outcomes. Bevan (2010) describes capacity in terms of there being enough people to execute QI initiatives and capability as the confidence and skills achieved by training to direct QI initiatives. Several studies evaluated whether QI training programs built capability, using pretest posttest analysis or by measuring successful implementation of a QI initiative (Filardo et al., 2009; Kaminski et al., 2012; McGrath & Blike, 2015; Morganti, Lovejoy, Haviland, Haas, & Farley, 2012; Pearson, Needleman, Beckman, & Han, 2016; Ruud et al., 2012; Schilling et al., 2010; Vackerberg, Levander, & Thor, 2016). But individual capability is not enough. Organizations must have adequate numbers of people with these skills to build capacity to sustain QI efforts. Both capacity and capability are considered essential to sustain QI

initiatives (Bevan, 2010; Chassin & Loeb, 2013; Kaminski, Schoettker, Alessandrini, Luzader, & Kotagal, 2014).

In 2016, a 600-bed acute care tertiary safety net medical center implemented the Quality Academy Program (QAP) to provide formal interdisciplinary training in QI with intent to build capacity and capability. The QAP's six-month course encompasses didactic and experiential elements to provide participants with the tools and skills to complete QI projects. Wave 1 (March 2016 –September 2016), Wave 2 (September 2016 –March 2017), and Wave 3 (April 2017 – October 2017) have completed this training. Staff and leadership have enthusiastically supported the training, but an evaluation of the program is needed to determine whether it is adequately building capacity and capability.

Purpose of the Project

The purpose of this project is to identify the evidence-based curriculum components predicting sustainable QI capacity and capability and to determine whether those components exist in the QAP.

Research Questions, Goals and Objectives

The questions to explore in this project are:

1. What are the evidence-based elements of QI training programs that lead to sustainable capacity and capability?
2. Does the QAP incorporate these evidence-based elements in its training program?
3. Do participants who graduate from the QAP gain knowledge of QI principles and practices (e.g., do they gain capability)?

4. Do participants in the QAP continue to design and implement QI projects after they graduate (e.g., is the program building capacity)?
5. Do the projects completed by QAP participants result in improved patient outcomes?

Supporting Framework

This project includes program and learning evaluation components. Therefore, two synergistic supporting frameworks guided this work. The Logic Model framed the program evaluation and Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning directed the evaluation of participant learning.

The Logic Model

The Logic Model, developed by Joseph S. Wholey, has been used to evaluate large public programs since its inception in the early 1970's (McLaughlin & Jordan, 2004; Millar, Simeone, & Carnevale, 2001; Weiss, 1997; Wholey, 1972). The model focuses attention holistically on the program to determine whether the proposed outcomes are realistic given the resources used. In this model, *inputs* are the resources such as personnel, services, or financial costs that go into the program. *Activities* are actions planned or completed with the inputs provided. *Outputs* are the outcomes of the inputs plus activities, and can be material goods, projects, services, or reports. The *short, intermediate, and long-term outcomes* are the program goals. Describing specific outcomes allows for development of appropriate metrics to determine program effectiveness which is consistent with the principles of QI (McLaughlin & Jordan, 2004).

Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning

Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning is a widely used methodology to evaluate the short and longer-term effects of training adult learners (Dorri, Akbari, & Dorri Sedeh, 2016; Kirkpatrick, 1979; Rouse, 2011; Slater, Lawton, Armitage, Bibby, & Wright, 2012; Smidt, Balandin, Sigafos, & Reed, 2009; Steensma & Groeneveld, 2010). The four levels of learning are: (1) reaction, (2) learning, (3) behavior, and (4) results. Level 1 (reaction) is considered the lowest level of achievement, while Level 4 (results) is the highest and measures ability to synthesize and apply knowledge. Each level builds from the prior. The reaction phase gathers participant's initial perceptions of the course using post course evaluations, e.g. did they like it. Then, learning is measured with pre and post surveys, and behavior is appraised by review of performance after training. The results phase can include application of training to job performance or, more broadly, increased employee satisfaction and improved morale (Kirkpatrick, 1979).

Integrating the QAP Logic Model and Kirkpatrick's Learning Levels

For this project, the Logic Model was used to evaluate overall program effectiveness in building capacity and capability, while Kirkpatrick's model was used to evaluate individual learners' capability. The Levels of Learning framework is embedded within the program evaluation to provide a more comprehensive view of the QAP, allowing assumptions to be made about capability and capacity in sustaining QI initiatives.

Inputs. For the QAP, the inputs include characteristics brought by both participants and the hospital. This distinction clarifies the evidence-based elements unique to each input and delineates the contributions of both to the overall outcome of

building capacity and capability (Figure 1). The items italicized in Figure 1 depict those items identified in the literature as significant in predicting capacity and capability (Callahan, 2015; Eid & Quinn, 2017; Ramar, Hale, & Dankbar, 2015; Ruud et al., 2012). The inputs for the participant include their individual motivation, curiosity, and interpersonal skills. Studies suggest that these intrinsic factors have some influence on successfully achieving capability (Daugherty et al., 2013; Eid & Quinn, 2017; Jeffs, Abramovich, et al., 2013). Inputs for the hospital include the training materials, curriculum, and expert faculty. The culture of the organization and willingness to release employees to work on QI projects are additional hospital inputs (Blake, Kohler, Culler, Hawley, & Rask, 2012; Clegg, Rees, & Titchen, 2010; Morganti et al., 2014; Schilling et al., 2011; Stieber, 1991; Wong, Goguen, & Shojanian, 2013).

Activities and outputs. Activities and outputs include course attendance, mentorship by QI experts, lectures, understandable didactic content, and completion of course skills assessments that lead to development of capability (Geisz, 2013; Medina et al., 2015; Mochan & Nash, 2015; Ruud et al., 2012; Schattenkirk, 2012; Schilling et al., 2011; Stieber, 1991). For the QAP, activities included structured course material with in-class activities designed to build skills in using QI tools. Other activities included teamwork exercises and learning style assessments for participants to use with their QI teams. The QAP participants were placed in teams during class activities to practice skills being taught.

Short-term, intermediate and long-term outcomes. Short-term outcomes are those that develop capability, while the long-term outcomes are those that lead to

Figure 1. Supporting framework for the Quality Academy Program adapted from the Logic Model

capacity (Mery, Dobrow, Baker, Im, & Brown, 2015; Scanlon, Beich, et al., 2016; Schattenkirk, 2012; Schilling et al., 2011; Wong et al., 2013). For the QAP, the short-term outcomes for the participants were increased self-reported proficiency and expressed confidence in QI skills. For the hospital, the short-term outcomes were identification of gaps in evidence-based elements predicting attainment of capacity and capability. The intermediate outcomes for participants included leading additional QI projects. For the hospital, intermediate outcomes were those that suggested the building of capacity (e.g. generating a waiting list for the QAP and diffusion of QI knowledge across the organization). The ultimate results were improved patient outcomes and sustained capacity and capability, with individual participants transitioning to QI mentor roles and 250 trained mentors within five years.

Program evaluation. The program evaluation serves as the feedback loop to incorporate lessons learned and fills gaps identified within the program. For the QAP, the evaluation of learners seeks to identify characteristics of successful participants, while the evaluation of the program identifies content that needs modification. Between each Wave of the QAP, program content was refined based on end of course evaluations and specific feedback from participants and leadership observations. In this model, program evaluation was envisioned as an ongoing, continuous feedback loop.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A literature search was conducted to explore the concepts of QI capacity and capability using computerized databases, including PubMed, CINAHL, Google Scholar, ERIC, PsychInfo, EBSCO, Sage, ProQuest Dissertation and Thesis, and Wiley Online. Search terms in various combinations included QI, quality management, continuous quality improvement, QI training programs, QI capacity, QI capability, building capacity, building capability, QI curriculum, QI culture, training evaluation, competency development, organizational culture, implementation science, program evaluation, and training transfer. Date delimitations were set to the last fifteen years (2003-2017) in an effort to retrieve the most current information. This timeframe was chosen to coincide with the expansion of QI training recommendations by the IOM (IOM, 2003). One earlier article on QI and organizational culture was retrieved outside of the date delimitations because of the unique insights in provided into this subject (Shortell et al., 1995).

In addition to searching established databases, references from the Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) and the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) were searched to identify relevant sources of information. Articles referenced in systematic reviews, annotated bibliographies, and dissertations relevant to QI training were retrieved.

Articles were English only, original qualitative or quantitative research articles, systematic reviews, peer-reviewed articles, and annotated bibliographies citing QI training programs in any country and any health care setting. These articles were organized into the non-discrete categories of (a) building capacity and capability, (b) organizational success, (c) participants' experiences, and (d) curriculum (Appendix A).

Building Capacity and Capability for Quality Improvement

Capability for QI reflects the skills, knowledge, and abilities to plan, develop, and implement strategies to improve clinical or operational performance. The literature reports a spectrum of educational approaches, from informal didactic content added to existing meetings, to formal didactic classes with pre-work, homework, and an assigned QI project. The attitudes of participants, the training structure, and individual support influence achieving capability. On the other hand, capacity for QI is dependent on having adequate numbers of capable staff. Organizational factors such as adequate support, leadership, and an innovative culture lead to successful capacity. The literature acknowledged both capacity and capability as interrelated components for effective application of QI initiatives.

Organizations used different strategies to build capacity and capability for QI with mixed results. In a randomized controlled study across 47 hospitals, the intervention group received QI training to address community acquired pneumonia and congestive heart failure metrics (Filardo et al., 2009). Both groups improved, reflecting limited effects from QI training. In another large-scale implementation of QI across 16 community health centers, Scanlon, Alexander, et al. (2016) found no differences in outcomes between communities who had training and those that did not. Alternatively, Lee, Aziz, Singhal, and Cronin (2015) and Whippy et al. (2011) improved the use of evidence-based guidelines using QI training, showing statistically significant improvements in outcomes. Daniel et al. (2016) used informal QI training within an established multidisciplinary group to improve clinical outcomes in an intensive care unit. The mixed results suggest other contextual factors, such as organizational,

participant, or curriculum components influencing successful achievement of capacity and capability.

More commonly, studies revealed QI principles taught through formal curriculum that included experiential projects and mentorship as part of the course (Kaminski et al., 2014; Kaminski et al., 2012; McGrath & Blike, 2015; McNab, McKay, & Bowie, 2015; Rao, Carballo, Cummings, Millham, & Jacobson, 2016; Rask et al., 2011; Riley, Parsons, Duffy, Moran, & Henry, 2009; Schilling et al., 2010). The completion of projects by participants suggests capability, while the number of projects completed demonstrates capacity. McGrath and Blike (2015) reported completion of 124 projects over 20 months after completion of a training program for their 10,000 employees. Schilling et al. (2010) reported 49 projects across 22 medical centers with aggregate completion rates of 84%.

While these studies address realization of intermediate outcomes, few studies have empirically tested the long-term sustainability of QI training (Rask et al., 2011; Schilling et al., 2010). Blake et al. (2012) examined the value of investment in QI, recording an improvement in their organization's quality ranking among national academic medical centers from the 45th percentile to the 10th percentile. Schilling et al. (2010) reported a 61% increase in improvement capacity measured by expert observation. The ability to measure success with reliability across organizations is impeded by the lack of formal evaluation tools and methods (Morganti et al., 2012; Schilling et al., 2011).

Organizational Culture and Quality Improvement Capacity

Organizational culture influences whether QI capacity is achieved and sustained. Apekey, McSorley, Tilling, and Siriwardena (2011) found a positive correlation between

leadership's behavior and a culture of innovation, predicting the use of QI tools in practice. In measuring culture directly through surveys, the literature shows that training will not build capacity without a supportive culture. Cultural characteristics such as trust and open communication predicted sustained use of QI tools (Bobiak et al., 2009; Callahan, 2015; Morganti et al., 2014; Shortell et al., 1995).

White, Wells, and Butterworth (2014) examined work engagement as a cultural construct, noting that work engagement was statistically higher in units trained in QI. Similarly, Babich et al. (2016) and Zoutman and Ford (2017) found a stronger QI culture in organizations that supported a QI infrastructure (e.g. investing in staff and other resources to support QI) rather than those who just provided QI training. In a qualitative study of primary care providers, Goldberg, Mick, Kuzel, Feng, and Love (2013) found that leadership support for innovation influenced willingness to engage in QI activities. Eid and Quinn (2017) and Mery et al. (2015) identified contextual elements influencing organizational success including those of the work environment and relationship with co-workers. A compilation of the evidence-based elements influencing organizational success is included in Table 1.

Participant Characteristics and Quality Improvement Capacity

Participants in QI training programs included physicians, nurses, administrators, and ancillary staff. Ruud et al. (2012) noted that participants across educational levels showed the same ability to make improvements. Kaminski et al. (2014) recommended training for leadership first, before front line staff, to ensure organizational support. Others recommended front line training and engagement (Daugherty et al., 2013; Parker et al., 2009). Most studies trained multidisciplinary staff. Some studies mentioned staff

Table 1

Elements Influencing Organizational Success

Element	Identified in one source ¹	Identified in multiple sources
Capacity for change		X
Culture of innovation (learning culture)		X
Adequate infrastructure to support QI		X
Work relationship		X
Trust	X	
Open Communication		X
Teamwork		X
Accountability	X	
Resource Allocation		X
Outcome Monitoring		X
Data collection assistance	X	
Sufficient, expert faculty		X
Safety Culture		X
Inter-organizational sharing	X	
Emphasis on front line training		X
Strategic alignment to organization		X
Leadership engagement		X
Standardized approach to QI		X

Note: ¹(Eid & Quinn, 2017)

volunteering for QI training, others did not describe how the participants were chosen. One study recommended choosing participants with specific personality characteristics such as curiosity, humility, and conscientiousness (Eid & Quinn, 2017). Participants also described QI training as an opportunity for professional growth which may have influenced their choosing to enroll (Jeffs, Lo, Beswick, & Campbell, 2013).

Participant's attitudes influenced whether QI continued post training. Positive attitudes towards change were predictive of successful QI project completion in several studies (Eid & Quinn, 2017; Phillips, Hebish, Mann, Ching, & Blackmore, 2016). Negative attitudes towards QI were attributed to lack of time to conduct QI projects, perception of more work associated with QI activities, non-supportive organizational culture, and inadequate resources for QI activities (Goldberg et al., 2013; P. Parker, 2015; Siverbo, Eriksson, Raharjo, & Moonen, 2014; Watts, Augustine, & Lawrence, 2009). Participants who did not complete the program or did not attend all sessions were less successful at implementing projects (Filardo et al., 2009; Ruud et al., 2012). Projects surrounding specific clinical goals were more likely to have staff involved that had interest in improving the work environment. The evidence-based participant characteristics influencing success are included in Table 2.

Curriculum Characteristics and Quality Improvement Capacity

The literature reported a variety of curricula used to train staff in QI. Most studies included a combination of didactic and experiential training with a culminating project (Bethune et al., 2016; Blake et al., 2012; Brownlee, Minnier, Martin, & Greenhouse, 2013; Daugherty et al., 2013; Davis, Cornett, Mahanna, See, & Randolph, 2016; Eid & Quinn, 2017; Estrada et al., 2012; Fieldston et al., 2016; Fok & Wong, 2014; Gupta, Ringer, Tess, Hansen, & Zupancic, 2014; Kaminski et al., 2014; Kaminski et al., 2012; Majka et al., 2013; Masters, 2015; McGrath & Blike, 2015; McNab et al., 2015; McNamara, Rafferty, & Fitzpatrick, 2016; Morganti et al., 2012; Rask et al., 2011; Riley, Parsons, Duffy, et al., 2009; Runnacles, Moulton, & Lachman, 2013; Schattenkirk, 2012; Sockalingam, Stergiopoulos, Maggi, & Zaretsky, 2010; Vackerberg et al., 2016; Wong et

al., 2013). Specific courses covered in the QI curriculum were not described in detail. General course descriptions included courses in developing a QI project, some basic statistical analysis, and courses covering concepts and tools used in QI.

Table 2

Elements Influencing Participant's Success

Element	Identified in one source	Identified in multiple sources
Positive attitude towards change		X
Motivation to learn		X
Mental processing skills	X ¹	
Interpersonal skills & ability to work in teams		X
Curiosity		X
Humility	X ¹	
Conscientiousness		X
Resilience		X
Wisdom	X ¹	
Support from manager/supervisor		X
Professional interest		X
QI part of job duties	X ²	
Multidisciplinary		X
Time to complete project		X

Note: ¹ (Eid & Quinn, 2017), ² (Joly, Booth, Mittal, & Shaler, 2012)

Two studies reported using the natural work environment to engage staff in QI activities, such as the “transforming care at the bedside (TCAB)” model (Pearson et al., 2016) or “releasing time to care (RTC)” (Wright & McSherry, 2013). With these models, staff nurses are engaged to improve their work environment using QI tools taught informally. Another novel approach used a flipped classroom, where prework included

self-directed learning followed by demonstration and practice of concepts in a classroom setting (Ramar et al., 2015).

Most QI training programs developed their own QI models using portions of commercially available programs such as Six Sigma, Lean, or the Model for Improvement (Apekey et al., 2011; Babich et al., 2016; Brownlee et al., 2013; Cornett et al., 2012; Daugherty et al., 2013; Eid & Quinn, 2017; Estrada et al., 2012; Filardo et al., 2009; Fok & Wong, 2014; Holmboe, Prince, & Green, 2005; Kaminski et al., 2014; Kaminski et al., 2012; Masters, 2015; McNab et al., 2015; Morganti et al., 2012; Parker et al., 2009; Ramar et al., 2015; Rao et al., 2016; Riley, Parsons, McKoy, et al., 2009; Rivard, Parker, & Rosen, 2013; Ruud et al., 2012; Scanlon, Alexander, et al., 2016; Schilling et al., 2010; Sellers et al., 2013; Sockalingam et al., 2010; Wong et al., 2013). An advantage to using a combination approach was the ability to tailor the training to the organization's culture and use portions of each program to build a more comprehensive training program. Disadvantages included the preparation time required to develop the curriculum internally or financial constraints if experts were brought in for training.

The literature strongly advocated the use of mentors to assist with QI projects during training episodes, though the studies did not mention whether the mentors were also faculty in the QI training program (Adams et al., 2015; Fok & Wong, 2014; Gupta et al., 2014; Jeffs, Lo, et al., 2013; Maski et al., 2014; Masters, 2015; McNab et al., 2015; McNamara et al., 2016; Mery et al., 2015; Morgan, 2012; Pearson et al., 2016; Runnacles et al., 2013; Schattenkirk, 2012; Schilling et al., 2010; Starr et al., 2016; Stille, Savageau, McBride, & Alper, 2012; Whippy et al., 2011). Mentors were described as experts in QI who provided coaching and assistance with various aspects of the QI projects. They were

deployed as 1:1 partners with participants or were assigned to multiple participants as a team for the duration of the program. Barriers to the use of mentors included not enough trained staff to function as mentors, especially in the early stages of program development, and the expense of hiring experts in mentor roles. The evidence-based elements of curriculum reported in studies and systematic reviews are listed in Table 3.

Measures of Success in Building Capacity and Capability

The literature reported a variety of methods to determine whether a program was successful in building capacity or capability. Pre and post surveys were a common theme in measuring short-term capability. Surveys were most commonly completed immediately post training, with some programs repeating surveys at intervals of six months, 12 months, or both post training (Kaminski et al., 2012; McNab et al., 2015; Morganti et al., 2012; Rask et al., 2011; Runnacles et al., 2013; Ruud et al., 2012). Improvements in QI knowledge post training demonstrated statistical significance overall. Other measures of success included completion of QI projects started in training, additional projects completed post training, or sharing QI tools learned with coworkers after completing training (Blake et al., 2012; Brownlee et al., 2013; Cornett et al., 2012; Rao et al., 2016; Rask et al., 2011). These measures may indicate whether capacity for QI is diffusing.

Many studies used Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning model to identify success using post training surveys (Bethune et al., 2016; Davis et al., 2016; Kaminski et al., 2012; Kislov, Waterman, Harvey, & Boaden, 2014; McNab et al., 2015; Ramar et al., 2015; Riley, Parsons, McKoy, et al., 2009; Ruud et al., 2012; Schilling et al., 2010; Starr et al., 2016; Wong, Etchells, Kuper, Levinson, & Shojania, 2010; Wong et al., 2013).

Table 3

Curriculum Elements Influencing Success

Element	Identified by one source	Identified by multiple sources
Properly scoped project		X
Pre-work and homework		X
Multidisciplinary team-based learning		X
Didactic taught by experts		X
Content includes ethical considerations	X ¹	
Content includes change management		X
1:1 mentors as part of the curriculum for project support and advice		X
Validated assessment tools		X
Natural work environment for projects		X
Statistical assistance	X ²	
QI tool learning linked to projects		X
Beginner, intermediate and advanced courses		X
Use case studies		X
Include QI vocabulary & terms		X
Various modalities (online, distance, flipped classroom) geared toward specific participants		X
Grounded in science of improvement and change management		X
Activities to teach QI (e.g. red bed game, Lean LEGO® exercise)	X ³	X
Adapt training to learning styles	X ⁴	

Notes: ¹ (Czabanowska et al., 2012) ² (Ruud et al., 2012) ³ (Brownlee et al., 2013) ⁴ (Blake et al., 2012)

The highest levels achieved were Levels 2 and 3, meaning that the program resulted in behavior changes related to QI as a result of participation, but organization-wide change was not objectively analyzed. No studies suggested that one curriculum was preferred

over another. The most common thread was training around use of QI tools, regardless of commercial source.

Skill building in the use of QI tools was commonly measured post training, either empirically by review of project performance, or more subjectively through self-reported surveys. Other self-reported responses included participants' confidence to lead QI initiatives post training, noting that increased confidence may predict continued use of learned QI skills (Blake et al., 2012; Cornett et al., 2012; Davis et al., 2016; Fok & Wong, 2014; Hess, Johnston, Lynn, Conforti, & Holmboe, 2013; Masters, 2015; McNab et al., 2015; Pearson et al., 2016; Ramar et al., 2015; Runnacles et al., 2013; Sellers et al., 2013).

The literature strongly supports attainment of capability following QI training, specifically when training is formalized and accompanied by mentorship. The literature is less clear about when capacity is achieved. Several large-scale programs successfully trained sizeable numbers of staff without objective measures of capacity. In a recent systematic review, Mery, Dobrow, Baker, Im, and Brown (2017) summarized the scarcity of evidence available to measure capacity and concluded that important gaps exist. While Mery et al. (2017) seek objective economic evidence (e.g. return on investment [ROI] related to training), perhaps an initial step to address capability and capacity would be to evaluate the ability of QI training programs to diffuse knowledge and skills across an organization.

METHODS

Setting

This project was conducted in a 600-bed acute care tertiary safety net medical center with participants who completed the QAP. The QAP, a six-month program open to nurses, physicians, support staff, and administrative staff, provides didactic and experiential training in QI methods. Three “Waves” of the QAP have been completed (Wave 1: March 2016 – September 2016, Wave 2: September 2016 – March 2017 and Wave 3: April 2017 – October 2017). The goals of this program are to build capacity and capability amongst hospital staff to initiate and lead QI projects.

Research Questions

A quasi-experimental pretest posttest design was used to answer five research questions:

1. What are the evidence-based elements of QI training programs that lead to sustainable capacity and capability?
2. Does the QAP incorporate these evidence-based elements in its training program?
3. Do participants who graduate from the QAP gain knowledge of QI principles and practices (e.g., do they gain capability)?
4. Do participants in the QAP continue to design and implement QI projects after they graduate (e.g. is the program building capacity)?
5. Do the projects completed by QAP participants result in improved patient outcomes?

Sample

The participants were hospital employees (nurses, physicians, administrative staff, and ancillary staff) who completed the QAP. For the first Wave, all participants were hand selected by nursing and quality department leadership to participate in the pilot program. For Wave 2 and Wave 3, ten (out of 30 and 26, respectively) were selected by nursing leadership and the remainder self-selected based on advertisements distributed across the hospital (Appendix I). For all three Waves, participants were required to obtain their supervisor's approval prior to enrollment. The total combined sample for all three Waves was 77 participants. Of these, several did not complete the program and a few did not complete both a pre and post survey; therefore, the sample analyzed in this study was 63.

Demographic information was collected on the pre and post surveys and reviewed by the QAP faculty. The demographic information included, participant's name, the department they worked in, their professional designation, how many years they had been in their profession, and whether they had any prior experience with QI. Appendix B includes copies of the surveys with the full demographics collected.

Ethical Considerations

The QAP program was implemented prior to starting this project. Surveys and program content had been previously created. No informed consent was obtained prior to requesting completion of the surveys. Surveys were distributed and collected electronically using Survey Monkey®. Names were collected on the surveys as a means of tracking completion of the surveys by the QAP administrative staff. The names were redacted from the data provided to this investigator by QAP administrative staff.

Information on departments and years of experience was requested by this investigator in aggregate to minimize the chance of connecting individual data with participants.

Applications were submitted to the hospital and the university Institutional Review Board (IRB) and were deemed exempt as a QI study (Appendix C). Hospital permission was obtained to use aggregate results of the surveys as a secondary dataset to conduct statistical tests of significance (Appendix D).

Data Analyses

The QAP collected self-reported survey results as an administrative function of the program. These surveys were distributed at three intervals, immediately pre Academy, immediately post Academy and 6-months post Academy. Survey questions were Likert-type scales requesting levels of proficiency and confidence in using QI tools and conducting QI projects (Appendix B).

QAP Logic Model & Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning

This project asked five research questions within the framework of the QAP Logic Model and Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning. Research Questions 1, 2, and 3 were aligned with the short-term outcomes defined by the QAP Logic Model and Kirkpatrick's Levels 1 and 2. These included participant satisfaction with the program, improved proficiency in QI confidence and skills, and identification of gaps in evidence-based elements in the QAP. For Research Questions 1 and 2, descriptive tabular analyses were described. For Research Question 3, paired samples t-tests were conducted to assess for differences in self-reported proficiency before and after completing the QAP. Mixed methods analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to assess for differences between Waves. Chi-square and Kruskal Wallis rank sum tests were done to evaluate differences

between waves and expected versus observed responses to post survey questions. Qualitative content analysis was conducted to identify themes for selected questions with open-ended responses and descriptive tabular results were presented for project outcomes. Details on each statistical test and its relationship to the QAP Logic Model and Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning are provided in Table 4.

Kirkpatrick's Level 1 (reaction) assesses participants' reaction to the program (e.g. did they like it). The QAP collected post course surveys from participants at the conclusion of each of the eight didactic courses for all Waves (Appendix H). The end of course surveys were optional and not all participants completed them for each course. A descriptive analysis of satisfaction with the course was completed to assess for Level 1 learning.

Research Question 4 aligned with the intermediate outcomes, leading a QI project within six months of completing the Academy and diffusing QI knowledge across the organization. Statistical analysis on post survey questions related to confidence and success in meeting goals were conducted using Kruskal-Wallis and Chi-squares tests (Table 4).

Research Question 5 aligned with the long-term outcomes of improved patient outcomes, desire to continue QI education, and Kirkpatrick Level 4 (reaction) which measures whether there has been an improvement in organizational performance (Kirkpatrick, 1979). Level 4 is considered the ultimate results of the training program. Chi-square analysis of questions 11 and 12 on the 6-month post survey (Appendix B) and descriptive analysis of completed projects using project templates were compiled to address these outcomes (Table 4).

Table 4

Structure for Statistical Data Analysis: Relationship between Logic Model and Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning

	Logic (Short-term) & Kirkpatrick (Level 1, Level 2)	Logic (Intermediate-term) & Kirkpatrick Level 3	Logic (Long-term) & Kirkpatrick (Level 4)
Research Q1 EB	Descriptive Analysis Tabular Presentation		
Research Q2 QAP	Descriptive Analysis Tabular Presentation with gap analysis		
	Paired T-tests Wave 1 Paired T-tests Wave 2 Paired T-tests Wave 3 Pre survey Q7, Q8 Q9, Q10 Q11 Post survey Q3, Q4, Q5, Q6,Q7 (test for differences between pre post for each Wave)		
Research Q3, Capability	Mixed Methods ANOVA Wave 1, Wave 2, Wave 3 Pre survey Q7, Q8 Q9, Q10 Q11 Post survey Q3, Q4, Q5, Q6, Q7 (Test for differences between waves pre/post)		
	Qualitative Content Analysis Open ended responses to Q9, 11,12,13,14,15 (Identify themes)		
	Descriptive statistics Post Course Survey Q9 (overall) Excellent (Which class session did they like the most/least		

Table 4, *cont.*

	Logic (Short-term) & Kirkpatrick (Level 1, Level 2)	Logic (Intermediate-term) & Kirkpatrick Level 3	Logic (Long-term) & Kirkpatrick (Level 4)
		Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum Wave 1, Wave 2 and Wave 3 Post Q8 (confidence) Chi-square Wave 1, Wave 2, Wave 3 Post Q12 (successful) Post Q11 (met goals)	
Research Q4 Capacity, continue QI		Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum Wave 1 and 2 only 6M_Post Q6 –(project status continued) Chi-square Goodness of Fit 6M_Post_Q7 (updated data) 6M_Post Q8 (more PDSA) 6M_Post Q9 (spread) 6M_Post Q10 (more QI)	
Research Q5 Improved patient outcomes			Chi-square Goodness of Fit Wave 1 and Wave 2 6M_Post Q11 (mentor) 6M_post Q12 Descriptive Table Project templates

Notes: 6M_Post = six month post survey, EB = evidence-based, QAP = Quality Academy Program, QI = quality improvement

RESULTS

Sample Demographics

A total of three Waves comprising 77 staff enrolled in the QAP (as of October, 2017) and 69 completed the program for an overall completion rate of 90%. After eliminating incomplete data (e.g., non-paired surveys), a sample size of 63-paired (e.g., pre and post) surveys was available for analysis. Most participants were inpatient registered nurses who had less than five years in practice or more than 20 years in practice. More paired surveys were available for Waves 2 and 3 due to closer monitoring of survey responses by QAP administrative personnel. Participants in Waves 1 and 2 completed an additional 6-month post Academy survey for a sample size of 49 surveys. Across all Waves, a total of 63 QI projects were completed. A summary of the demographic information is presented in Table 5.

Evidence-Based Elements of QI Training

During the literature review for this study, the focus was on elements reported as having influenced training programs that were successful in building capacity and capability. These were separated into the categories of organizational, participant, and curriculum elements (Tables 1, 2, and 3). Only elements appearing in multiple sources were considered evidence-based using the definition of non-propositional knowledge described by Rycroft-Malone et al. (2004), where evidence can be derived informally through practice as opposed to research.

The literature supports 39 evidence-based elements that led to capacity and capability (Tables 1, 2, and 3). The QAP Logic Model included these evidence-based elements as inputs and activities for both the participant and the hospital (Figure 1).

Table 5

Demographic Data

	Wave 1		Wave 2		Wave 3	
	N	(%)	N	(%)	N	(%)
Enrolled (% of all 3 Waves)	21	(27%)	30	(39%)	26	(34%)
Completed QAP (% of enrolled)	19	(90%)	27	(90%)	23	(88%)
Completed Pre/Post Survey (% of enrolled)	14	(66%)	25	(83%)	24	(92%)
Project completed (% of completed course)	15	(79%)	26	(96%)	22	(96%)
Years in Profession						
<5	5	(36%)	4	(16%)	7	(29%)
6-10	2	(14%)	7	(28%)	4	(17%)
11-15	4	(29%)	4	(16%)	2	(8%)
16-20	0	(0%)	2	(8%)	5	(21%)
>20	3	(21%)	8	(32%)	6	(25%)
Department						
Administration	4	(21%)	6	(21%)	3	(12%)
Ancillary	5	(26%)	8	(28%)	3	(12%)
Corrections	0	(0%)	2	(.07%)	3	(12%)
Inpatient	7	(37%)	8	(28%)	10	(38%)
Outpatient	3	(16%)	5	(17%)	7	(27%)
Professional Discipline						
Administrator	2	(10%)	1	(.03%)	5	(19%)
Clerical	1	(.05%)	2	(.07%)	2	(.08%)
Clerical Supervisor	0	(0%)	0	(0%)	1	(.04%)
CRNA	1	(.05%)	0	(0%)	0	(0%)
Facilities	1	(.05%)	0	(0%)	0	(0%)
Registered Nurse	9	(47%)	15	(54%)	9	(35%)
Nurse Manager	1	(.05%)	3	(11%)	6	(23%)
Nurse Practitioner	0	(0%)	1	(.03%)	1	(.04%)
Physician	1	(.05%)	2	(.07%)	1	(.04%)
Physician Assistant	0	(0%)	0	(0%)	1	(.04%)
Respiratory Therapist	4	(21%)	3	(11%)	0	(0%)
Social Worker	0	(0%)	1	(.03%)	0	(0%)

Note: Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Inclusion of Evidence-Based Elements in the QAP

Organizational Elements

In evaluating whether the organizational elements were present, this investigator reflected on experience within the organization as the Chief Quality Officer, comments made by participants in their evaluations, and knowledge of the organization's strategies and approaches to QI. Each element was reviewed carefully with attention to how this element was demonstrated within the organization. Partial scores were assessed for the elements of "adequate infrastructure to support QI", "resource allocation", and "safety culture" based on comments in the first two Waves related to the lack of time allowed to conduct the QI project. For safety culture, this investigator reflected on an organization-wide Patient Safety Culture Survey where a low response rate (11%) and empirical results suggested a less than ideal safety culture. Of the 14 evidence-based elements for organizational success, the QAP met 11 of them (79%) completely and the remaining three elements (21%) partially. Table 6 presents elements influencing organizational success and whether they exist within the QAP.

Table 6

Elements Influencing Organizational Success in QAP

Element	Identified in multiple sources	Present in Quality Academy
Capacity for change	X	X
Culture of innovation (learning culture)	X	X
Adequate infrastructure to support QI	X	Partial
Work relationship	X	X
Open Communication	X	X
Teamwork	X	X
Resource Allocation	X	Partial
Outcome Monitoring	X	X
Sufficient, expert faculty	X	X
Safety Culture	X	Partial
Emphasis on front line training	X	X
Strategic alignment to organization	X	X
Leadership engagement	X	X
Standardized approach to QI	X	X

Participants' Elements

Table 2 suggests the evidence-based elements for participant success. These elements included such things as personal motivation and professional interest. Although not explicitly stated, this investigator assumed that a majority of the participants exhibited these characteristics through active participation in each workshop, completion of a culminating project, and comments made on end of course surveys. Of the ten elements for participant success, the QAP program participants demonstrated nine of them (90%). Partial credit was given to “time to complete project” as this was one of the

main concerns expressed by participants verbally throughout the course. Table 7 includes the participants' elements for the QAP.

Table 7

Elements Influencing Participant's Success in QAP

Element	Identified in multiple sources	Present in Quality Academy
Positive attitude towards change	X	X
Motivation to learn	X	X
Interpersonal skills & ability to work in teams	X	X
Curiosity	X	X
Conscientiousness	X	X
Resilience	X	X
Support from manager/supervisor	X	X
Professional interest	X	X
Multidisciplinary	X	X
Time to complete project	X	Partial

Curriculum Elements

Curriculum elements for success were identified in the literature review and presented in Table 3. After careful comparison with the curriculum elements in each Wave, four elements were identified as gaps in the QAP, despite curriculum modifications between Waves (See Appendix E for a summary of curriculum changes). Of the 15 elements, the QAP incorporated 11 of them (73%) but lacked content related to change management, inclusion of validated assessment tools, use of case studies, and use of varying modalities. Table 8 presents the analysis of curriculum elements present in the QAP.

Table 8*Curriculum Elements Influencing Success in QAP*

Element	Identified by multiple sources	Elements present in QAP
Properly scoped project	X	X
Pre-work and homework	X	X
Multidisciplinary team-based learning	X	X
Didactic taught by experts	X	X
Content includes change management	X	No
1:1 mentors as part of the curriculum for project support and advice	X	X
Validated assessment tools	X	No
Natural work environment for projects	X	X
QI tool learning linked to projects	X	X
Beginner, intermediate and advanced courses	X	No
Use case studies	X	No
Include QI vocabulary & terms	X	X
Various modalities (online, distance, flipped classroom) geared toward specific participants	X	No
Grounded in science of improvement and change management	X	X
Activities to teach QI (e.g. red bed game, Lean LEGO® exercise)	X	X

Overall, of the 39 evidence-based elements reporting successful building of capacity and capability, the QAP incorporates 30 (77%) of them completely, four of 39 (10%) partially, and five of 39 (13%) are missing.

Does the QAP Develop Capability?

Respondents from each Wave were asked to report their levels of proficiency across several domains both pre and post Academy. Using IntellectusStatistics™

software, paired samples t-tests were performed on each of the subcomponents within the five domains of (a) knowledge of QI models, (b) knowledge of QI tools, (c) knowledge of analytical and statistical tools, (d) knowledge of the QI process, and (e) knowledge of leading and sustaining QI (Appendix B). Paired samples t-tests compare the means of two groups. In this study, the groups were pre Academy and post Academy. Each paired sample included between four and 13 subcomponents for testing.

Prior to this analysis, for all t-tests, the data was evaluated for missing values and normal distribution assumptions using features contained within the software (IntellectusStatistics, 2017). Less than 5% of the values were missing, so data was imputed for these values as allowed per consultation with a statistician (O. Korosteleva, personal communication, October 20, 2017). Fourteen of the 64 variables (22%) had <5% missing data imputed.

Additionally, prior to the analysis, for all t-tests, IntellectusStatistics™ performed tests to address assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variance. Given the small sample sizes for this data set ($n = 14$ in Wave 1; $n = 25$ in Wave 2; and, $n = 24$ in Wave 3), the assumptions of normality can be questioned. A Shapiro-Wilk test (to evaluate whether the data was normally distributed) demonstrated mixed results, therefore, a Wilcoxon signed rank test was substituted where Shapiro-Wilk was significant (Razali & Wah, 2011). The Wilcoxon signed rank test is a non-parametric alternative to the paired samples t-test and does not share its distributional assumptions (Conover & Iman, 1981). Therefore, when Shapiro-Wilk was significant, a Wilcoxon signed rank test V statistic was reported (Tables 9-13).

Levene's test for equality of variance was used to assess whether the homogeneity of variance assumption was met (Levene, 1960). The homogeneity of variance assumption requires the variance of the dependent variable to be approximately equal in each group. The results of Levene's test were mixed. Since equal variances could not be assumed, Welch's t-test was used instead of the Student's t-test when Levene's test was significant (Ruxton, 2006). This is noted in Tables 9-13.

The null hypothesis for the paired samples t-test was that there would be no differences between the mean pre and the mean post self-reported proficiency scores. The alternative hypothesis was that there would be a difference in mean self-reported scores that was significantly different from zero, reported with p values. The magnitude of the differences between the matched scores is reported with Cohen's d , where a score of > 0.8 represents a greater magnitude of difference (IntellectusStatistics, 2017). See Tables 9-13.

Proficiency in Knowledge of QI Models

For proficiency in knowledge of QI models, participants were asked their level of proficiency in understanding (a) Lean, (b) Six Sigma, (c) Model for Improvement (MFI) and, (d) Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA). The mean scores across Waves pre Academy ranged from 0.21 to 0.96. (0 = not at all proficient, 1 = somewhat proficient, 2 = proficient, 3 = very proficient, and 4 = extremely proficient), with the lowest mean scores in knowledge of Six Sigma. Post Academy, the mean scores were statistically improved at a $p < .001$ level (ranging from 1.54 to 2.92) where 2 represents the score of "proficient" on the Likert scale for that question (Appendix B). The highest post Academy mean scores were for PDSA and the lowest means for Six Sigma. The effect

size, reported with Cohen's d , ranged from 1.42 to 3.35; with the highest effect score for Wave 3 in knowledge of Lean. A larger effect size indicates a greater difference in mean scores between groups (IntellectusStatistics, 2017). These results reflect respondents' self-report of having achieved proficiency in understanding several QI models post QAP. Table 9 provides results of the statistical tests for knowledge in QI Models.

Table 9

Paired Samples t-test for the Differences Pre and Post Academy – Proficiency in Knowledge of QI Models

		Pre Academy	Post Academy	Student's <i>t</i> -test or Welch's <i>t</i> -test			Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test				
		<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Median Pre</i>	<i>Median Post</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
Wave 1 (n = 14)	Lean	0.50 (0.85)	2.00 (0.88)	-5.51	< .001	1.73	--	--	--	--	--
	Six Sigma	0.31 (0.85)	1.54 (0.88)	-5.33	< .001	1.42	0.00	1.00	0.00	-3.03	.002
	MFI	0.43 (0.65)	2.36 (0.84)	-7.24	< .001	2.57	0.00	2.00	0.00	-3.22	.001
	PDSA	0.71 (0.83)	2.57 (0.94)	-5.95	< .001	2.10	--	--	--	--	--
Wave 2 (n = 25)	Lean	0.32 (0.80)	1.84 (0.80)	-8.72	< .001	1.90	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.19	< .001
	Six Sigma	0.16 (0.47)	1.60 (0.65)	-10.12*	< .001	2.55	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.31	< .001
	MFI	0.40 (0.58)	2.04 (0.84)	-9.04	< .001	2.27	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.19	< .001
	PDSA	0.60 (0.96)	2.16 (0.69)	-9.51	< .001	1.87	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.23	< .001
Wave 3 (n = 24)	Lean	0.21 (0.41)	2.16 (0.71)	-17.13	< .001	3.35	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.42	< .001
	Six Sigma	0.21 (0.43)	1.77 (0.87)	-9.06*	< .001	2.26	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.01	< .001
	MFI	0.55 (0.91)	2.45 (0.96)	-9.72	< .001	2.04	0.00	2.00	0.00	-3.99	< .001
	PDSA	0.96 (1.00)	2.92 (0.83)	-11.90	< .001	2.13	1.00	3.00	0.00	-4.36	< .001

Note. MFI = Model for Improvement, PDSA = plan-do-study-act Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 13 (Wave 1), 24 (Wave 2), and 23 (Wave 3). *d* represents Cohen's *d*, *V* = sum of the signed rank tests; used to compute the *z*; *z* = test used to compute the *p*; * = Levene's test was significant, so Welch's *t*-test was used instead of student's *t* test, -- Shapiro-Wilk not significant so no Wilcoxon reported

Proficiency in Knowledge of QI Tools

On the pre Academy survey, participants were asked to assess their level of proficiency using 13 different QI tools (Appendix B). On the post Academy survey, one of the tools was mistakenly left off for all Waves (conducting a waste walk) so this element was not assessed. The mean scores pre Academy ranged from 0.02 to 0.96, corresponding to “not at all” and approaching “somewhat proficient”. The lowest scores across Waves were for completing an A3, which is problem-solving tool used in the Lean model. The highest mean scores were in ORCHID reports, which are the organization’s electronic health record reports used to generate data from electronic patient health records. However, post Academy, for Waves 1 and 3, ORCHID reports did not reach significance at the $p < .001$ level, suggesting limited improvement in proficiency. Post Academy, the mean scores across all Waves were statistically significantly increased to a range of 1.48 to 2.83 indicating a value of higher than “somewhat proficient” and slightly less than “very proficient”. The highest post Academy mean scores were in conducting a PDSA, which was emphasized in the course curriculum. The lowest were for ORCHID reports in Waves 2 and 3. ORCHID reports were not emphasized in the curriculum in any Wave and were included to gauge experience of the group in the use of this tool, rather than in assessing pre and post improvement. The largest effect sizes, as reported with Cohen’s d , were in Wave 3 with the 5S tool (4.82), indicating substantial improvement between pre and post Academy scores. The lowest effect size was in Wave 3 with ORCHID reports. Table 10 includes results of the self-reported proficiency in the use of quality improvement tools.

Table 10

Paired Samples t-test for the Differences Pre and Post Academy – Proficiency in Use of Quality Improvement Tools

	Pre Academy	Post Academy	Student's <i>t</i> -test or Welch's <i>t</i> -test			Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test					
	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Median Pre</i>	<i>Median Post</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>	
5 whys	0.21 (0.51)	2.50 (0.83)	-11.76	< .001	3.32	--	--	--	--	--	
Value stream mapping	0.21 (0.58)	1.93 (0.83)	-8.83	< .001	2.40	0.00	2.00	0.00	-	3.24	.001
Creating a project charter	0.36 (0.74)	2.29 (0.83)	-11.72	< .001	2.45	0.00	2.00	0.00	-	3.40	< .001
Completing a PI template	0.50 (0.76)	2.29 (0.83)	-6.85	< .001	2.25	--	--	--	--	--	--
Conducting PDSA cycles	0.43 (0.65)	2.36 (0.84)	-7.24	< .001	2.57	0.00	2.00	0.00	-	3.34	< .001
Completing an A3	0.02 (0.08)	1.71 (0.73)	-8.78*	< .001	3.28	0.00	2.00	0.00	-	3.34	< .001
Process flow mapping	0.57 (0.76)	2.14 (0.95)	-5.40	< .001	1.83	--	--	--	--	--	--
5S	0.14 (0.53)	1.91 (0.83)	-6.78*	< .001	2.53	--	--	--	--	--	--
Driver diagrams	0.15 (0.31)	2.43 (0.85)	-9.51*	< .001	3.56	--	--	--	--	--	--
Benchmark data	0.33 (0.61)	2.14 (0.66)	-8.30	< .001	2.85	--	--	--	--	--	--
ORCHID reports	0.80 (0.71)	2.07 (1.27)	-3.50	.004	1.24	--	--	--	--	--	--
Fishbone diagrams	0.29 (0.61)	2.00 (0.88)	-7.77*	< .001	2.27	0.00	2.00	0.00	-	3.35	< .001

Table 10, *cont.*

		Pre Academy	Post Academy	Student's <i>t</i> -test or Welch's <i>t</i> -test			Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test				
		<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Median Pre</i>	<i>Median Post</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
Wave 2 (n = 25)	5 whys	0.24 (0.52)	1.96 (0.98)	-7.82*	< .001	2.19	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.07	< .001
	Value stream mapping	0.20 (0.58)	1.48 (0.71)	-7.60*	< .001	1.97	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.02	< .001
	Creating a project charter	0.28 (0.54)	2.04 (0.79)	-10.59	< .001	2.60	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.35	< .001
	Completing a PI template	0.32 (0.56)	1.84 (0.69)	-10.64	< .001	2.43	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.39	< .001
	Conducting PDSA cycles	0.48 (0.71)	2.16 (0.80)	-9.85	< .001	2.22	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.37	< .001
	Completing an A3	0.09 (0.28)	1.80 (0.82)	-9.32*	< .001	2.80	0.00	2.00	1.00	-4.27	< .001
	Process flow mapping	0.28 (0.54)	1.92 (0.86)	-8.61	< .001	2.28	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.20	< .001
	5S	0.12 (0.44)	2.12 (0.78)	-10.95*	< .001	3.16	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.38	< .001
	Driver diagrams	0.24 (0.44)	1.92 (0.95)	-9.33*	< .001	2.27	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.26	< .001
	Benchmark data	0.28 (0.61)	1.64 (0.86)	-7.51	< .001	1.82	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.09	< .001
	ORCHID reports	0.48 (0.65)	1.64 (1.04)	-6.82	< .001	1.34	0.00	2.00	0.00	-3.92	< .001
	Fishbone diagrams	0.44 (0.58)	1.60 (0.76)	-7.77	< .001	1.71	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.04	< .001

Table 10, *cont.*

		Pre Academy	Post Academy	Student's <i>t</i> -test or Welch's <i>t</i> -test			Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test				
		<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Median Pre</i>	<i>Median Post</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
Wave 3 (n = 24)	5 whys	0.21 (0.51)	2.50 (0.83)	-11.76*	< .001	3.32	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.26	< .001
	Value stream mapping	0.12 (0.34)	2.21 (0.83)	-13.16*	< .001	3.28	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.38	< .001
	Creating a project charter	0.33 (0.64)	2.50 (0.88)	-10.54	< .001	2.81	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.27	< .001
	Completing a PI template	0.33 (0.70)	2.50 (0.93)	-12.23	< .001	2.63	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.36	< .001
	Conducting PDSA cycles	0.71 (0.91)	2.83 (0.92)	-9.68	< .001	2.33	0.00	3.00	0.00	-4.24	< .001
	Completing an A3	0.04 (0.20)	2.42 (1.02)	-11.02*	< .001	3.24	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.25	< .001
	Process flow mapping	0.38 (0.71)	2.46 (0.88)	-12.30	< .001	2.60	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.39	< .001
	5S	0.04 (0.20)	2.58 (0.72)	-17.27*	< .001	4.82	0.00	3.00	0.00	-4.37	< .001
	Driver diagrams	0.42 (0.65)	2.50 (0.93)	-11.59	< .001	2.59	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.28	< .001
	Benchmark data	0.25 (0.68)	2.29 (1.00)	-10.48*	< .001	2.39	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.36	< .001
	ORCHID reports	0.96 (1.12)	1.77 (1.18)	-4.45	< .001	0.71	1.00	2.00	13.00	-3.28	.001
	Fishbone diagrams	0.75 (0.74)	2.04 (0.91)	-5.64	< .001	1.56	--	--	--	--	--

Note: Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 13 (Wave 1), 24 (Wave 2), and 23 (Wave 3). *d* represents Cohen's *d*., *V* = sum of the signed rank tests; used to compute the *z*; *z* = test used to compute the *p*; * = Levene's test was significant, so Welch's *t*-test was used instead of student's *t* test, -- Shapiro-Wilk not significant so no Wilcoxon is reported.

Proficiency in Use of Analytical and Statistical Tools

The next domain asks for self-reported proficiency in the use of analytical and statistical tools. These tools included the use of statistical charts, Pareto charts, scatter plots, frequency distributions, and run charts. The mean scores pre Academy across all Waves ranged from 0.20 to 0.54, representing levels closer to “not at all” proficient. Post Academy, there were four exceptions to statistically significant improvement in Wave 1; these were Pareto charts, scatter plots, frequency distributions, and run charts. This is likely due to the poorly received data course and the lack of faculty understanding of the participants’ limited experience with MS Excel®. This course was completely changed for Waves 2 and 3, and the improved mean scores with statistical significance suggests this was a positive improvement. In Wave 1, participants were overwhelmed with learning the use of MS-Excel® to organize data while also learning to use statistical control charts and tools. In subsequent Waves, the data analysis course sessions were split so that participants could concentrate on MS Excel® skills in Part 1 and statistical analysis in Part 2. Statistically significant differences between pre and post Academy scores suggest this strategy was beneficial for learning. The mean scores post Academy across elements ranged from 0.96 to 2.17 indicating levels of “somewhat proficient” to “proficient”. The largest effect sizes, as shown with Cohen’s *d*, were in run charts for Waves 2 and 3. In the redesigned class, run charts were emphasized at several different points in the curriculum. Table 11 presents the results for self-reported proficiency in the use of analytical and statistical tools.

Table 11

Paired Samples t-test for the Differences Pre and Post Academy – Proficiency in Use of Analytical and Statistical Tools

		Pre Academy	Post Academy	Student's t-test or Welch's t-test			Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test				
		<i>M (SD)</i>	<i>M (SD)</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Median Pre</i>	<i>Median Post</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
Wave 1 (n = 14)	Statistical charts	0.43 (0.76)	1.71 (0.91)	-5.83	< .001	1.53	--	--	--	--	--
	Pareto charts	0.21 (0.58)	1.25 (0.98)	-3.70*	.003	1.29	0.00	1.25	0.00	-2.56	.011
	Scatter plots	0.50 (0.94)	1.36 (1.01)	-3.12	.008	0.88	--	--	--	--	--
	Frequency distributions	0.43 (0.94)	1.36 (1.01)	-3.48	.004	0.95	0.00	1.00	0.00	-2.56	.010
	Run charts	0.50 (0.94)	1.86 (0.95)	-5.47	< .001	1.44	0.00	2.00	0.00	-3.00	.003
Wave 2 (n = 25)	Statistical charts	0.20 (0.41)	1.24 (0.83)	-7.69*	< .001	1.59	0.00	1.00	0.00	-4.10	< .001
	Pareto charts	0.20 (0.58)	1.16 (0.80)	-5.40*	< .001	1.38	0.00	1.00	7.00	-3.69	< .001
	Scatter plots	0.28 (0.61)	0.96 (0.84)	-3.99	< .001	0.92	0.00	1.00	6.50	-3.23	.001
	Frequency distributions	0.24 (0.52)	0.96 (0.79)	-4.55	< .001	1.08	0.00	1.00	0.00	3.49	< .001
	Run charts	0.28 (0.54)	1.88 (0.88)	-8.76	< .001	2.19	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.18	< .001
Wave 3 (n = 24)	Statistical charts	0.21 (0.66)	1.58 (0.88)	-8.75*	< .001	1.77	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.12	< .001
	Pareto charts	0.21 (0.51)	1.50 (0.98)	-7.85*	< .001	1.66	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.02	< .001
	Scatter plots	0.54 (0.78)	1.58 (1.18)	-6.80*	< .001	1.04	0.00	1.50	0.00	-3.85	< .001
	Frequency distributions	0.21 (0.51)	1.42 (0.78)	-8.21*	< .001	1.84	0.00	1.50	0.00	-4.04	< .001
	Run charts	0.29 (0.75)	2.17 (1.13)	-10.21*	< .001	1.96	0.00	2.00	0.00	-4.27	< .001

Note. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 13 (Wave 1), 24 (Wave 2), and 23 (Wave 3). *d* represents Cohen's *d*, *V* = sum of the signed rank tests; used to compute the *z*; *z* = test used to compute the *p*; * = Levene's test was significant, so Welch's *t*-test was used instead of student's *t* test, -- Shapiro-Wilk not significant so no Wilcoxon is reported

Proficiency in Managing the QI Process

Respondents were next asked for self-reported proficiency in managing elements within the QI process. These included, (a) defining the problem statement, goals and scope of a project, (b) aligning projects to the mission, values, strategic, and business priorities, (c) managing a project to ensure the project meets milestones and goals, and (d) tracking, monitoring, and communicating project progress to all stakeholders; and (e) managing a team.

Pre Academy, participants reported mean scores of 0.96 to 1.58 indicating levels between somewhat proficient and proficient, with the lowest means in the topic of strategic alignment in Wave 2. Post Academy means ranged from 2.00 to 2.75 indicating levels of proficiency between “proficient” and “very proficient”. For Wave 1, only scores in strategic alignment improved at a statistical significance of $p < .001$. For Waves 2 and 3, curriculum changes were made to emphasize project management and stakeholder communication (Appendix E). Specific course content on team dynamics and team management were added to the curriculum, and faculty and mentors worked with participants to scope the project into one that was manageable within a six-month time frame. In addition, participants were asked to complete a skills checklist with their mentors (Appendix F) and identify barriers earlier in their project timeline. The improved statistical significance demonstrated in Waves 2 and 3 suggest these were positive improvements. This is also reflected in the effect size reported with Cohen’s d , for Wave 3, where the effect size (measures of the magnitude of difference) was large (1.22 to 1.48). Results of the proficiency in managing the QI process are presented in Table 12.

Table 12

Paired Samples t-test for the Differences Pre and Post Academy –Proficiency Managing the QI Process

		Pre Academy	Post Academy	Student's t-test or Welch's t-test			Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test				
		<i>M (SD)</i>	<i>M (SD)</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Median Pre</i>	<i>Median Post</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
Wave 1 (n = 14)	Problem statement, goals and scope	1.07 (1.07)	2.14 (0.86)	-4.37	< .001	1.10	1.00	2.00	4.00	-2.83	.005
	Strategic alignment	1.00 (1.04)	2.29 (0.91)	-4.50	< .001	1.31	--	--	--	--	--
	Project management	1.00 (1.04)	2.00 (0.88)	-2.88	0.13	1.04	--	--	--	--	--
	Stakeholder communication	1.07 (1.00)	2.07 (0.92)	-3.89	.002	1.04	--	--	--	--	--
	Managing teams	1.36 (1.08)	2.07 (0.73)	-2.92	.012	0.77	--	--	--	--	--
Wave 2 (n = 25)	Problem statement, goals and scope	1.12 (0.88)	2.20 (0.71)	-6.65	< .001	1.35	1.00	2.00	8.50	-4.02	<.001
	Strategic alignment	0.96 (0.79)	2.16 (0.62)	-7.86	< .001	1.69	1.00	2.00	0.00	-4.15	< .001
	Project management	1.16 (0.90)	2.00 (0.82)	-4.94	< .001	0.98	1.00	2.00	0.00	-3.53	< .001
	Stakeholder communication	1.20 (0.91)	2.08 (0.81)	-5.28	< .001	1.02	1.00	2.00	6.50	-3.58	< .001
	Managing teams	1.32 (1.03)	2.00 (0.82)	-3.78	< .001	0.73	1.00	2.00	24.00	-3.04	.002
Wave 3 (n = 24)	Problem statement, goals and scope	1.29 (1.08)	2.71 (0.81)	-6.55	< .001	1.48	1.00	3.00	5.00	-3.93	< .001
	Strategic alignment	1.21 (1.10)	2.54 (0.93)	-5.37	< .001	1.30	--	--	--	--	--
	Project management	1.25 (1.19)	2.58 (0.97)	-5.26	< .001	1.23	--	--	--	--	--
	Stakeholder communication	1.25 (1.15)	2.67 (0.82)	-6.82	< .001	1.42	1.00	3.00	5.00	-3.91	< .001
	Managing teams	1.58 (0.93)	2.75 (0.99)	-5.45	< .001	1.22	1.00	3.00	4.50	-3.60	< .001

Note. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 13 (Wave 1), 24 (Wave 2), and 23 (Wave 3). *d* represents Cohen's *d*, *V* = sum of the signed rank tests; used to compute the *z*; *z* = test used to compute the *p*; * = Levene's test was significant, so Welch's *t*-test was used instead of student's *t* test, -- Shapiro-Wilk not significant so no Wilcoxon is reported

Proficiency in Leading and Sustaining QI

The final domain on the self-reported survey asks for proficiency in leading and sustaining QI in, (a) promoting a culture of continuous improvement, (b) communicating vision, expectations, and PI project clearly and consistently to stakeholders, (c) identifying barriers that impede change, (d) improvement sustainability measures to achieve and sustain improvement, (e) providing education, training and tools for effective implementation of process and workflow changes, and (f) leading a performance improvement team. Mean scores pre Academy ranged from 0.79 to 1.58 (“not at all” to “somewhat proficient”) with lower scores for sustainability and leading teams. Post Academy, mean scores ranged from 1.92 to 2.62 (“proficient” to “very proficient”). In Wave 1, only “leading teams” reached a level of statistical significance between pre and post Academy scores. In Wave 2, “providing tools for change” did not reach statistical significance at a $p = < .001$ levels. Looking at effect sizes reported with Cohen’s d , in Wave 3, all results demonstrated a large effect size, meaning that the difference between pre Academy and post Academy was substantial. The improved scores overall in Wave 3 suggest that the curriculum improvements made between Waves did have a positive effect on self-reported proficiency. Table 13 presents the results of the proficiency in leading and sustaining QI.

Table 13

Paired Samples t-test for the Differences Pre and Post Academy – Proficiency in Leading and Sustaining Quality Improvement

		Pre Academy		Student's t-test or Welch's t-test			Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test				
		<i>M (SD)</i>	<i>M (SD)</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>Median Pre</i>	<i>Median Post</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
Wave 1 (n = 14)	Promoting QI culture	1.50 (0.94)	2.29 (0.61)	-4.20	.001	0.99	1.50	2.00	6.00	-2.94	.005
	Vision & expectations	1.36 (1.01)	2.07 (0.83)	-4.37	< .001	0.77	1.00	2.00	0.00	-2.89	.004
	Identifying barriers	1.43 (0.94)	2.36 (0.74)	-5.64	< .001	1.10	1.00	2.50	0.00	-3.13	.002
	Sustainability	0.96 (1.09)	2.21 (0.58)	-5.48	< .001	1.44	1.00	2.00	0.00	-2.99	.003
	Providing tools for effective change	1.36 (0.93)	2.07 (0.73)	-2.50	0.27	0.86	--	--	--	--	--
	Leading Teams	0.79 (1.19)	2.00 (0.78)	-4.32	< .001	1.21	--	--	--	--	--
Wave 2 (n = 25)	Promoting QI culture	1.48 (1.00)	2.20 (0.87)	-4.55	< .001	0.77	1.00	2.00	6.50	-3.35	< .001
	Vision & expectations	1.16 (1.14)	2.16 (0.75)	-5.77*	< .001	1.04	1.00	2.00	6.00	-3.70	< .001
	Identifying barriers	1.48 (1.05)	2.32 (0.80)	-6.10	< .001	0.90	1.00	2.00	0.00	-3.82	< .001
	Sustainability	1.08 (0.95)	1.92 (0.70)	-5.63	< .001	1.00	1.00	2.00	8.00	-3.72	< .001
	Providing tools for effective change	1.48 (0.96)	2.12 (0.83)	-3.53	.002	0.71	1.00	2.00	22.50	-2.91	.004
	Leading Teams	1.16 (0.99)	2.16 (0.94)	-5.77	< .001	1.04	1.00	2.00	0.00	-3.73	< .001
Wave 3 (n = 24)	Promoting QI culture	1.62 (1.06)	2.79 (0.98)	-5.67	< .001	1.15	--	--	--	--	--
	Vision & expectations	1.50 (0.98)	2.75 (0.85)	-7.23	< .001	1.37	1.00	3.00	8.50	-4.11	< .001
	Identifying barriers	1.58 (1.06)	2.67 (0.87)	-5.01	< .001	1.12	1.00	2.50	6.00	-3.56	< .001
	Sustainability	1.12 (1.12)	2.58 (0.78)	-5.17	< .001	1.52	--	--	--	--	--
	Providing tools for effective change	1.58 (1.10)	2.58 (0.97)	-4.28	< .001	0.96	--	--	--	--	--
	Leading Teams	0.96 (1.00)	2.62 (0.97)	-7.00	< .001	1.69	--	--	--	--	--

Note. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 13 (Wave 1), 24 (Wave 2), and 23 (Wave 3). *d* represents Cohen's *d*, *V* = sum of the signed rank tests; used to compute the *z*; *z* = test used to compute the *p*; * = Levene's test was significant, so Welch's *t*-test was used instead of student's *t* test, -- Shapiro-Wilk not significant so no Wilcoxon is reported

Analysis of Differences Between Waves

During this project, the QAP faculty continuously assessed post course surveys and participant feedback and made changes in curriculum and content to address concerns and gaps. A summary of the curriculum changes is provided in Appendix E. In order to determine whether these changes created differences in capability between Waves, the following dependent composite variables were created for the five domains:

- Pre Academy and post Academy proficiency in QI models;
- Pre Academy and post Academy proficiency in QI tools;
- Pre Academy and post Academy proficiency in statistical tools;
- Pre Academy and post Academy proficiency in QI process; and,
- Pre Academy and post Academy proficiency in leading and sustaining QI.

Using a mixed model analysis of variance (ANOVA) with one within-subjects factor (proficiency) and one between-subjects factor (Wave), the independent variable “Wave” was compared to the dependent composite variables.

Prior to the analysis, assumptions of univariate normality, homogeneity of variance, and sphericity were assessed using IntellectusStatistics™ (IntellectusStatistics, 2017) to evaluate the sample distribution and variances within the variables. Univariate normality assesses whether the variable is normally distributed, homogeneity of variance is a measure of how equivalent the variances are between the variables, and sphericity measures the combined variances between each variable used in the repeated measures test. Most of the pre Academy composite variables were not normally distributed across Waves for the pre Academy composite scores, thus the ANOVA should be interpreted with caution.

The mean composite scores for each of the five domains pre Academy were between “not proficient” and “somewhat proficient”, while the post Academy scores were between “proficient” and “very proficient”, consistent with the paired samples t-test results using individual elements (Table 14). There were statistically significant results for the within factor component, validating the differences in mean scores between the pre Academy composites and the post Academy composites. Furthermore, the η_p^2 statistic (partial eta squared) describes the main effect to be related to the differences between the pre and post composite scores rather than any differences between Waves (IntellectusStatistics, 2017). Between Waves, no significant differences were found, meaning that the curriculum changes between Waves had no effect on the means of pre or post composites (Table 15).

Table 14

Means and Standard Deviations for Factor Level Combinations

Wave	Pre Academy Proficiency in QI Models	Post Academy Proficiency in QI Models	Row Average
1	1.93 (2.87)*	8.41 (3.01)	5.17 (4.38)
2	1.48 (2.31)*	7.64 (2.53)	4.56 (3.93)
3	1.88 (2.23)*	9.18 (2.89)	5.53 (4.49)
Column Average	1.73 (2.38)	8.40 (2.82)	5.06 (4.24)
Note: 0 = not proficient, 4 = somewhat proficient, 8 = proficient, 12 = very proficient, 16 = extremely proficient			
Wave	Pre Academy Proficiency in QI Tools	Post Academy Proficiency in QI Tools	Row Average
1	4.01 (4.93)*	25.27 (7.59)	14.64 (12.51)
2	3.45 (4.56)*	22.12 (7.80)	12.79 (11.35)
3	4.54 (4.94)*	28.61 (8.71)	16.57 (14.03)
Column Average	3.99 (4.74)	25.29 (8.49)	14.64 (12.70)
Note: 0 = not proficient, 12 = somewhat proficient, 24 = proficient, 36 = very proficient, 48 = extremely proficient			

Table 4., *cont.*

Wave	Pre Academy Proficiency in Statistical Tools	Post Academy Proficiency in Statistical Tools	Row Average
1	2.07 (3.91)*	7.54 (4.48)	4.80 (4.98)
2	1.20 (2.38)*	6.20 (3.43)	3.70 (3.86)
3	1.46 (2.52)*	8.25 (4.29)	4.85 (4.89)
Column Average	1.49 (2.80)	7.28 (4.05)	4.38 (4.53)

Note: 0 = not proficient, 5 = somewhat proficient, 10 = proficient, 15 = very proficient, 20 = extremely proficient

Wave	Pre Academy Proficiency in QI Process	Post Academy Proficiency in QI Process	Row Average
1	5.50 (4.77)*	10.57 (3.92)	8.04 (5.00)
2	5.76 (4.10)*	10.44 (3.28)	8.10 (4.37)
3	6.58 (5.15)*	13.24 (4.29)	9.91 (5.77)
Column Average	6.02 (4.62)	11.54 (4.00)	8.78 (5.12)

Note: 0 = not proficient, 5 = somewhat proficient, 10 = proficient, 15 = very proficient, 20 = extremely proficient

Wave	Pre Academy Proficiency in Leading QI	Post Academy Proficiency in Leading QI	Row Average
1	7.39 (5.51)	13.00 (3.72)	10.19 (5.43)
2	7.84 (5.58)	12.88 (4.49)	10.36 (5.62)
3	8.38 (5.47)	16.00 (5.06)	12.19 (6.48)
Column Average	7.94 (5.45)	14.10 (4.74)	11.02 (5.95)

Note: 0 = not proficient, 6 = somewhat proficient, 12 = proficient, 18 = very proficient, 24 = extremely proficient

Note. Standard deviations in parentheses, * = not normally distributed;

Table 15

One-Within One-Between ANOVA Results on Composite Proficiency Variables

	Source	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	η_p^2
Composite Proficiency in QI Models	Between-Subjects						
	Wave	2	23.28	11.64	1.17	.318	0.04
	Residuals	60	598.17	9.97			
	Within-Subjects						
	Within. Factor	1	1299.49	1299.49	363.90	< .001	0.86
	Wave: Within.Factor	2	8.30	4.15	1.16	.320	0.04
	Residuals	60	214.26	3.57			
Composite proficiency with tools	Between-Subjects						
	Wave	2	351.45	175.73	2.96	.060	0.09
	Residuals	60	3565.67	59.43			
	Within-Subjects						
	Within. Factor	1	13374.59	13374.59	454.38	< .001	0.88
	Wave: Within.Factor	2	178.37	89.19	3.03	.056	0.09
	Residuals	60	1766.08	29.43			
Composite proficiency with analytical & statistical tools	Between-Subjects						
	Wave	2	38.93	19.47	1.09	.344	0.03
	Residuals	60	1076.04	17.93			
	Within-Subjects						
	Within. Factor	1	972.47	972.47	157.44	< .001	0.72
	Wave: Within.Factor	2	20.58	10.29	1.67	.198	0.05
	Residuals	60	370.60	6.18			

Table 15, *cont.*

		Source	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	η_p^2
Composite proficiency with managing QI process	Between-Subjects							
		Wave	2	100.34	50.17	1.86	.164	0.06
		Residuals	60	1615.22	26.92			
	Within-Subjects							
		Within.Factor	1	879.74	879.74	92.08	< .001	0.61
		Wave: Within.Factor	2	25.85	12.93	1.35	.266	0.04
	Residuals	60	573.22	9.55				
Composite proficiency in leading QI	Between-Subjects							
		Wave	2	106.31	53.16	1.31	.278	0.04
		Residuals	60	2435.74	40.60			
	Within-Subjects							
		Within.Factor	1	1090.99	1090.99	101.14	< .001	0.63
		Wave: Within.Factor	2	43.53	21.77	2.02	.142	0.06
	Residuals	60	647.24	10.79				

Note: *df* = degrees of freedom, *SS* = sum of squares, *MS* = mean square, η_p^2 = partial eta squared

Qualitative Analysis of Capability

The post Academy survey included open ended questions which were evaluated using qualitative content analysis, seeking to identify patterns and themes from narrative responses (Polit & Beck, 2017). Elo and Kyngäs (2008) describe three phases of content analysis: preparation, organization and reporting. For this study, the preparation phase included determining the unit of analysis as the response to the question. The words used were taken verbatim without determining underlying or unspoken context. In the organizing phase, three faculty members from the QAP used inductive strategies to categorize and group the narrative responses to the open ended questions from the post Academy survey (questions 9, 11,12,13,14, and 15) into themes. These questions asked participants to, (a) identify something they learned from the QAP and how they incorporated this into their daily activities, (b) if they met their goals (why or why not), (c) whether they were successful in their process improvements (why or why not), (d) how they knew whether the results of the project were attributed to changes they made, (e) how they could sustain success, and (f) a final question for anything else they wanted to share. Three faculty members agreed upon themes prior to categorization of responses. One faculty member then categorized responses independently and shared results with the other two faculty members. The three faculty as a group chose the final categories through consensus. Results are recorded in Tables 16-21.

For the first question, “name something you learned from the QAP”, four themes emerged: specific tools, descriptions or revelations on QI concepts, attitudes towards QI, and teamwork in QI. . The most illustrative quotes from each of the themes are as follows:

Specific Tools

“ . . . flow charts, process mapping, 5s and team management”; “ . . . PDSA and process flow mapping”.

A common theme for specific tools included learning PDSA which is the Plan-Do-Study-Act cycle used in QI as a means to plan and implement small tests of change (Langley et al., 2009).

Descriptions or Revelations on QI concepts

“Data is powerful”.

Attitudes towards QI

“I really enjoyed learning how to make quality improvement changes at work. Most changes occur in a reactive manner and using the tools and the QA program provided, I’m able to find the [root cause]. On another note, I also learned change is not easy and planning for such changes occurs over time. Thus, barriers and challenges must be met head on, early on.”

Teamwork in QI

“That it is not just one person that can take a PI project and make all the changes, it requires an entire team for feedback and workload”.

The majority of responses addressed specific tools that participants’ incorporated into their daily activities. The most frequently cited tool was the PDSA process and flow mapping. Table 16 presents aggregate results of themes and their frequency distribution.

Table 16

Qualitative Themes for Question 9: Name Something You Have Learned from the Quality Academy Program and How You Have Incorporated That into Your Daily Activities

Theme	N	(%)
Specific tools	31	(48%)
Descriptions or revelations of QI concepts	13	(20%)
Attitudes towards QI	14	(21%)
Teamwork in QI	07	(11%)

The next questions asked whether respondents met their goals or not and why. Those respondents who reported meeting their goals attributed their success to having realistic and attainable goals, working collaboratively with their teams, and organizational support for their project. Those that failed to meet their goals attributed this to projects getting lost to organizational priorities, challenges with the time they allocated to the project, and inability to collect the data they needed to be successful. Many of those who partially met their goals noted that they were on target to achieve their goals, but the program was not long enough to realize goal attainment (these were scored as “yes” for the purposes of this study). A slightly larger number of respondents did not meet their goals. Table 17 provides a summary of responses.

Table 17

Qualitative Responses for Question 11: Have you met your goal? Why or Why Not?

Response	N	(%)
Yes	31	(47%)
No	35	(53%)

Question 12 asks whether the respondents were successful in their process improvements, why or why not. Respondents attributed their success to “*staff buy in*” and “*collaboration with management and frontline staff using tools of motivation and inspiration instead of manipulation*”. Many addressed the new skills they acquired in helping them frame and initiate process changes. Those who responded negatively ascribed challenges to not being able to initiate changes or not having enough time to work on their projects. A few addressed lack of buy in from colleagues and staff. Those who were partially successful described a work in progress and the expectation that the project would become successful with time. The majority was successful in their process improvements. Table 18 provides a summary of responses.

Table 18

Qualitative Responses for Question 12: Were you successful in the process improvements you initiated in your department? Why or Why Not?

Response	N	(%)
Yes	40	(61%)
No	26	(39%)

Question 13 asked how the participant knew that their results were attributable to changes they made. Three themes emerged from the response: attitudes, descriptive methods for measurement, and specific outcomes identified. Many respondents identified using data to detect changes in the process and analyzing data using baseline data and comparing data across time. Comments representative of the themes are noted below.

Attitudes

“Hopefully the data will support it but anecdotally a sense of change is palpable in the department, and their (sic) are more positive attitudes and less stress”

Descriptive methods for measurement

“Results can be directly attributed to the changes made by evaluating the data collected when the changes were made”.

Specific outcomes identified

“The drastic changes in our outcome measure that followed our interventions provide evidence that these changes were successful in achieving that goal. We validated these results by monitoring the appropriate balancing measures. Although there was some negative impact on these balancing measures, the positive impact on the outcome measure was much more substantial”

Most respondents provided a description of changes to their metrics to identify whether there were changes in their process, indicative of the emphasis on looking at and reviewing the data to determine whether changes made resulted in improvements. Table 19 presents aggregate results of themes.

Table 19

Responses to Question 13: How do you know that the results can be attributed to changes made?

Theme	N	(%)
Attitudes	3	(6%)
Descriptive methods for measurement	27	(51%)
Specific outcomes identified	23	(43%)

Question 14 asked how the respondents could sustain their success. Sustainability was added in Waves 2 and 3 as a specific course to provide information on how to maintain and continue improvements. Four themes emerged from the responses. These included: monitoring, communication, accountability and standardization. Examples of responses for each theme include:

Monitoring

“Random audits, continuing to keep staff knowledgeable when cycle times peak and continue to educate patients about arriving only 30 minutes prior to their appointment”.

Communication

“Continue to remind the staff to debrief and document that it was done. Post success in the resident workroom. Perhaps acknowledge success of various teams that work well together”.

Accountability

“I honestly believe that to sustain true success for the culture shift and change, (for my project or any PI project) that executives & management really come to the Gemba, sit down with frontline staff to discuss the issues, listen, provide positive feedback and support on at least a monthly basis to meet the first line of defenses’ needs. Then and only then can the frontline staff truly be the backbone (strength and support) of the organization”

Standardization

“We are building this type of work into our primary care structure and creating a standard template for how to perform outreach and close care gaps in our patients”.

Most respondents attributed sustainability to continued monitoring and communication, including incorporating new process changes into training sessions or creating communication tools for daily briefings. Monitoring in the form of audits was the most described theme. Table 20 reports the findings for Question 14.

Table 20

Qualitative Responses for Question 14: How can you sustain the success?

Theme	N	%
Monitoring	22	(35%)
Communication	20	(32%)
Accountability	12	(19%)
Standardization	9	(14%)

Question 15 advised that we value feedback and asked if there was anything else the respondent wished to share with us. The majority of the responses thanked the QAP for the opportunity to learn these new skills. Other themes included feedback on projects, the curriculum, and advice for mentors. Comments representative of the various themes are provided below.

Thankful

“I truly enjoyed this program. I think providing this type of education to employees can really promote a culture of quality because it lets the employees

know what our organization is doing. Thank you all for investing in me and I feel honored to have participated”.

Feedback on curriculum

“I believe this course was very valuable to my role as team coach. However, I would have liked a little more detail on some QI/PI tools including fishbone diagrams, control charts, pareto charts, and frequency distributions”.

Feedback on projects

“All of the information was helpful. The lectures were motivating, I just would like to have more time to work on the project”.

Feedback on mentors

“The mentors were all great and were critical to the understanding and application of all the concepts and tools.”

The majority of respondents was appreciative of the opportunity and expressed thanks to the Academy staff, their supervisors and senior leadership for the opportunities for professional growth and organizational contribution. Table 21 summarizes the responses.

Table 21

Responses to Question 15: We value your feedback

Theme	N	(%)
Thankful	19	(46%)
Feedback on curriculum	10	(24%)
Feedback on projects	5	(12%)
Feedback on mentors	7	(17%)

Note: Percentages may not equal 100% due to rounding.

Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning – Level 1 and Level 2 Analysis of Capability

In the QAP Logic Model (Figure 1), a short-term outcome includes an assessment of Kirkpatrick's Level 1 (e.g., did they like it) (Kirkpatrick, 1979). The QAP collected post course surveys from each of the didactic sessions asking nine questions on a five point Likert scale (1 = poor and 5 = excellent). Question 9 (overall evaluation of the course) was analyzed to assess participants' reaction to the program.

In the first Wave, course content was derived from faculty members' experiences and a review of the literature. The intent was to provide enough content for students to complete a project by practicing theories relevant to QI. The content focused on interactive sessions demonstrating key concepts. Two such interactive sessions are Robbie the Robot and paper airplanes. In Robbie the Robot, participants use a "robot" made from LEGOs® to learn the lean concepts of pull versus push flow and parallel versus batch processing. In paper airplane, participants learn the PDSA cycle by testing hypotheses in building a paper airplane to achieve the longest distance in flight. Both these classes were well received by participants.

In Wave 1, the course titled "fun with data" received the lowest score in overall satisfaction. As initially designed, this session was meant to provide concepts in statistical process control using an add-on program within MS Excel® that allows users to construct control charts. An important learning for the faculty after this course was that many participants had little skill with using MS Excel® to organize data or create charts, so the concepts of statistical process control were too advanced. In Wave 2, this course was split into two parts. The first part was included with the interactive paper airplane experience, where students used MS Excel® to organize data from each "flight". A

second data course was presented later in the Wave to build upon MS Excel® skills and to introduce statistical process control concepts.

With each Wave, course content was standardized such that any QAP faculty member could teach the course. This standardization ensured that the content was not faculty dependent and also allowed individual faculty members to enhance their skills by teaching different courses in each Wave. The consistent ratings for courses presented in all three Waves by different faculty seem to suggest that the course content was rated independent of the faculty. Lower scores in process mapping were surprising and bear further investigation. Figure 2 presents the aggregate percent of respondents rating the overall course very good or excellent as well as the Wave(s) the course was presented.

Is the QAP Building Capacity?

The key to continuing QI projects is having the confidence to complete a QI project. The QAP post Academy survey Question 8 asks participants how confident (3 = very confident, 2 = somewhat confident, 1 = not confident) they are in starting a QI project (Appendix B). Summary statistics and mean scores by Wave were calculated using IntellectusStatistics™ (2017). The observations of self-reported confidence had means of 2.64, 2.40, and 2.46 for Waves 1, 2, and 3 respectively, indicating values approaching “very confident”. Using IntellectusStatistics™ (2017), skewness and kurtosis were also calculated as a means to evaluate this variable’s distribution. When the skewness is greater than or equal to 2 or less than or equal to -2, then the variable is considered to be asymmetrical about its mean. When the kurtosis is greater than or equal to 3, then the variable's distribution is markedly different than a normal distribution in its tendency to produce outliers (Westfall & Henning, 2013). In this sample, based on the

values of kurtosis and skewness, the assumptions are that the distribution is symmetrical and normally distributed. An average of 2.4 to 2.6 indicates confidence levels between somewhat and very confident. Summary statistics for self-reported confidence are presented in Table 22.

Figure 2. Course satisfaction by wave.

Table 22

Summary Statistics Table for Interval and Ratio Variables Split by Wave

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>SE_M</i>	Skewness	Kurtosis
Self-Reported Confidence						
Wave 1	2.64	0.50	14	0.13	-0.60	-1.64
Wave 2	2.40	0.58	25	0.12	-0.27	-0.81
Wave 3	2.46	0.59	24	0.12	-0.49	-0.71

A Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test using IntellectusStatistics™ software (2017) was conducted to evaluate differences between Waves and was not significant ($X^2 = 1.63, p = .443$), indicating that the mean rank of self-reported confidence was similar for each Wave. A Kruskal-Wallis test is a non-parametric alternative to the one-way ANOVA and does not share the ANOVA's distributional assumptions that the variances between each group are equal (Conover & Iman, 1981). The lack of differences between Waves further illustrates the lack of effect of curriculum changes between Waves.

Confidence and continuing QI projects may also depend on whether there has been prior success in completing a project. Questions 11 and 12 on the post Academy survey ask whether the participant met the goals of their individual project and whether they were successful in the process improvements they initiated. The qualitative assessment discussed in the previous section showed a slight majority did not meet their goals, while most were successful in their process improvements. Results by Wave demonstrate Wave 3 reporting a majority of "yes" responses in meeting their goals and a majority in Wave 2 not successful in their process improvements (despite the full sample majority responding "yes"). Frequencies and percentages by Wave are presented in Table 23.

Table 23

Frequency Table for Nominal Variables

Wave	1	2	3
Have you met your goal?			
No	8 (12%)	16 (24%)	11 (17%)
Yes	7 (11%)	11 (17%)	13 (20%)
Were you successful in the process improvements you initiated?			
No	4 (6%)	14 (21%)	8 (12%)
Yes	11 (17%)	13 (20%)	16 (24%)

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

To test for differences between Waves, a Chi-square test of independence was conducted. This test was used to determine whether there was a relationship between Wave and meeting goals or success in process improvements. Prior to conducting the analysis using IntellectusStatistics™ (2017), the assumption of adequate cell size was assessed, which requires all cells to have expected values greater than zero and 80% of cells to have expected values of at least five (McHugh, 2013). Both conditions were met. The results of the Chi-square test were not significant for either question, similar to the prior evaluation on proficiency in the five domains. Table 24 presents the results of the Chi-square test.

Table 24

Observed and Expected Frequencies by Wave and Question 11 and 12

Question 11: Have you met your goal?		
Wave	No	Yes
1	8 [7.95]	7 [7.05]
2	16 [14.32]	11 [12.68]
3	11 [12.73]	13 [11.27]
Question 12: Were you successful in the process improvements you initiated in your department?		
Wave	No	Yes
1	4 [5.91]	11 [9.09]
2	14 [10.64]	13 [16.36]
3	8 [9.45]	16 [14.55]

Note. Questions 11 $X^2(2) = 0.92, p = .631$. Question 12 $X^2(2) = 3.14, p = .208$. Items in brackets represent expected cell frequencies.

Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning - Level 3 Analysis of Capacity

In the QAP Logic Model that informed this study (Figure 1), an intermediate goal is achieving Level 3, a change in behavior, in Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning. A change in behavior was operationally defined as continued use of QI techniques and/or implementation of additional QI projects post training. As part of its program, the QAP administered a survey to participants 6 months post completion of the QAP. Results for Waves 1 and 2 are available for this analysis (Wave 3 did not complete a post 6-month survey prior to completion of this project). Across both Waves, respondents reported a higher frequency of completing and transitioning their projects to sustainable everyday operations. They also reported not having updated their run charts or continued additional PDSA's. A majority reported not spreading their project to other units or participating in additional QI projects after completing the Academy. Most were not interested in

becoming a mentor. Descriptive analyses of questions 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 on the 6-month post survey (Appendix B) are presented in Table 25 for Waves 1 and 2.

Table 25

Frequency Table for Questions 6-11, 6 months after Wave 1

Question Responses	Wave 1 (n = 15)		Wave 2 (n = 23)	
	n	%	n	%
Question 6: Current status of your Quality Academy Project				
Complete and transitioned as a sustainable part of everyday operations	9	64%	11	44%
Complete, but no longer a part of everyday operations due to process changes	1	7%	3	12%
Not complete and no longer monitored	0	0%	2	8%
Not complete, but continuing to monitor and do QI work on it	4	29%	7	28%
Question 7: Since completing the QAP, have you made updates to your project's run chart?				
No	6	43%	16	64%
Yes	8	57%	8	32%
Question 8: Since completing the QAP, have you run any additional PDSAs?				
No	4	29%	17	68%
Yes	10	71%	7	28%
Question 9: Did you spread your QAP project to other units within the Medical Center?				
No	10	71%	18	72%
Yes	4	29%	6	24%
Question 10: Since completing the QAP, have you participated in or led one or more QI project?				
No	4	29%	6	24%
Yes - led	4	29%	2	8%
Yes- participated in	3	21%	10	40%
Yes - participated in & led	3	21%	6	24%
Question 11: Are you interested in becoming a mentor?				
No	9	64%	14	56%
Yes	5	36%	10	40%

Note. Due to rounding errors and missing data, percentages may not equal 100%.

In order to determine whether the frequencies reported were statistically significant, a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test using IntellectusStatistics™ (2017) was conducted for Question 6 which asks about the current status of their PI project. Responses included: (a) complete and transitioned as a sustainable part of everyday operations, (b) complete but no longer part of everyday operations due to process changes, (c) not complete but continuing to monitor and do QI work on it, (d) not complete and no longer monitoring, and (e) other. Responses were recoded to convert the variable to a scale with “complete and transitioned . . .” designated as a “4” (highest) to “not complete and no longer monitored” designated as a “1” (lowest), (“other” was not included). The results of the Kruskal-Wallis test were not significant ($\chi^2(1) = 0.53, p = .466$), indicating similar responses for each Wave.

To test for statistical significance for the remaining questions on the 6-month post Academy survey (7, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12) the Chi-square goodness of fit test was performed using IntellectusStatistics™ (2017). The Chi-square goodness of fit tests for differences between expected and observed values for a given variable, in this case likelihood of “yes” or “no” responses. For Wave 1, the results of the tests across all questions were not significant suggesting an equally likely yes or no response. For Wave 2, statistical significance was found for the “no” responses on running additional PDSAs, spreading the project to other units, and furthering education in QI, indicating a statistically significant higher observed “no” response than expected.

Question 10 did not return data due to insufficient observations within each cell. This question asked whether the respondent participated in or led other QI projects since completing the QAP. The responses were (a) no, (b) yes – led, (c) yes – participated in,

(d) yes – participated in and led. These variables were recoded to dichotomous yes-no responses in order to achieve sufficient cell sizes. A repeat Chi-square goodness of fit test was statistically significant in Wave 2 in that there were fewer observations than expected in the “no” response indicating more respondents participated in QI post Academy than were expected to participate or lead QI. Table 26 presents the results.

Does the QAP Improve Patient Outcomes?

A total of 63 projects were completed across all three Waves. Each participant completed a project template (Appendix G) to report his or her project outcomes. A data abstraction tool (Appendix J) loosely modeled after the Quality Improvement Knowledge Application Tool – revised (QIKAT –R) described in Singh et al. (2014) was developed by this investigator and used to assess each completed project template. Of the 63 completed projects, 16 identified a project aim to improve a patient outcome (as opposed to a project aim to improve a process). For example, project W106’s aim was to “reduce the number of patient falls from an average of 5.5 per 1000 patient day to 2.5 per 1000 patient day”. QAP faculty classified this project as improving a patient outcome. Alternatively, project W226’s aim was to “reduce operating room turnaround time”. QAP faculty classified this project as improving a process and not improving a patient outcome. While patient care would be improved if operating room turnaround time were reduced, the project was not specifically aimed at improving a patient outcome.

Table 26

Chi-square Goodness of Fit Tests for Questions 7-12

Question	Wave		Obs Freq	Exp Freq	$\chi^2(1)$	<i>p</i>
7. Since completing QAP have you updated your project's run chart?	1	No	6	7.00	0.29	.593
		Yes	8	7.00		
	2	No	16	12.00	2.67	.102
		Yes	8	12.00		
8. Since Completing QAP have you run additional PDSAs?	1	No	4	7.00	2.57	.109
		Yes	10	7.00		
	2	No	17	12.00	4.17	.041*
		Yes	7	12.00		
9. Did you spread your Quality Academy Program Project to other units?	1	No	10	7.00	2.57	.109
		Yes	4	7.00		
	2	No	18	12.00	6.00	.014*
		Yes	6	12.00		
10. Since completing the QAP, have you participated in or led one or more QI projects	1	No	4	3.50	0.29	.963
		Yes	4	3.50		
		Led	4	3.50		
	2	Yes participate	3	3.50	Insufficient observations to conduct analysis	
		Yes participate & led	3	3.50		
10. Since completing the QAP, have you participated in or led one or more QI projects <i>(revised to dichotomous variables due to insufficient observations)</i>	1	No	4	7.00	2.57	.109
		Yes	10	7.00		
	2	No	6	12.00	6.00	.014*
		Yes	18	12.00		
11. Are you interested in becoming a QI Mentor	1	No	9	7.00	1.14	.285
		Yes	5	7.00		
	2	No	14	12.00	0.67	.414
		Yes	10	12.00		
12. Since completing QAP, have you furthered your education in QI	1	No	10	7.00	2.57	.109
		Yes	4	7.00		
	2	No	20	12.00	10.67	.001*
		Yes	4	12.00		

Note: * = Statistical significance at $p < .05$

The project aims, measures, charts, PDSA action plans, long-term sustainability, and outcomes were scored across 2-3 dichotomous variables for a total possible score of 17. This investigator scored all 63-project templates, resulting in average scores of 13 to 14 across Waves. In order to establish inter-rater reliability, two other QAP faculty independently scored a total of 13 templates (six for faculty one [F1] and seven for the faculty two [F2]). Percent agreement was calculated as described by McHugh (2012). The percent agreement was 73% (F1 = 77%; F2 = 70%). McHugh (2012) describes agreements greater than 51% as acceptable for inter-rater reliability. Areas of highest disagreement between faculty reviewers included interpreting whether the project included appropriate balancing measures, whether the project included a sustainability measure that was permanent and whether charts were annotated with PDSA's. A surprising result was the high disagreement with whether charts were annotated with PDSA's, which should not have required judgment. A discussion determined that F1 assumed all charts required annotation, not just the process and outcome charts.

A majority of all projects showed improvements at the end of the program, even though they did not all meet their goals. Of the 16 projects with aims to improve patient outcomes, all of Wave 1, all of Wave 2, and three of five in Wave 3 showed improvements at the end of the program. Four of the six projects in Wave 1 met their defined goal, two of the five projects in Wave 2 met their goal and one of five projects in Wave 3 met their goal. A few of the most impressive examples of project outcomes include:

- Hand off communication improved by 57%
- Reduced fall rate from 5.5/1000 patient days to 3.3/1000 patient days

- Reduced the number of endotracheal tube pressure ulcers from 16/month to 4/month
- Reduced central line associated blood stream infection (CLABSI) rate to 0 on one nursing unit (sustained for 4 months)

Descriptive data on the project templates is provided in Table 27.

Table 27

Project Template Analysis

	Wave1	Wave 2	Wave 3
Total projects (n = 63)	15	26	22
Average Score (of 17)	13	14	14
Met Goal (% of total)	6 (40%)	9 (35%)	13 (59%)
Showed Improvement	14 (93%)	23 (88%)	18 (82%)
Projects improving outcomes	6	5	5
Average scores (of 17)	14	14	14
Met Goal	4 (67%)	2 (40%)	1 (20%)
Showed Improvement	6 (100%)	5 (100%)	3 (60%)

Kirkpatrick's Levels of Learning - Level Four

Participants are informed at the beginning of the course that they have an opportunity to become a mentor in the QAP after having completed an additional three QI projects post Academy graduation. In order to gauge interest in becoming mentors, question 11 on the 6-month post Academy survey asks whether participants are interested in becoming mentors. Results of Chi-square analysis using IntellectusStatistics™ (2017) were previously reported in Table 26 and were not statistically significant for either Wave (Wave 1 $p = .285$; Wave 2, $p = .414$).

DISCUSSION

Medical errors continue to plague the health care field (James, 2013). The IOM's repeated calls to action include specific recommendations to conduct training in QI (IOM, 1999; IOM, 2000; IOM, 2001; IOM, 2003). Training in formal QI methodologies can equip frontline staff with the knowledge and confidence to address these errors by implementing QI projects designed to improve processes and outcomes that influence patient care (Chassin & Loeb, 2013). This study identified and compiled a broad list of evidence-based elements aimed at achieving capacity and capability to conduct QI initiatives. Understanding the evidence-based elements of QI training programs across three dimensions (organizations, curriculum, and participants) may provide useful information for others who want to develop programs that target improvement capability in individuals and capacity in organizations. This study used a descriptive gap analysis, a quasi-experimental pretest posttest design and a qualitative content analysis using self-reported survey data of an existing QI training program to determine whether the program is building capacity and capability to improve patient outcomes.

The Quality Academy Program (QAP), a 6-month didactic and experiential program, began in March 2016 at a 600-bed acute care tertiary safety net medical center and has graduated three Waves with a total of 77 participants since its inception. A comprehensive literature review identified 39 evidence-based elements influencing achievement of capacity and capability in individuals and organizations. In designating these elements as evidence-based, this investigator relied upon a definition of "evidence-based" described by Rycroft-Malone et al. (2004) where use of knowledge that comes from the local context of practice is distinguished from research evidence that is

empirically derived. The evidence-based elements considered in this study were derived from multiple studies, though few were randomized and controlled. Nevertheless, they present a form of evidence that may be relied upon to inform practice.

The QAP incorporated 30 (77%) of these evidence-based elements into its formal quality improvement training; however, important gaps exist. Key among these gaps was adequate infrastructure to support QI. The participants expressed frustration in their efforts to participate due to competing organizational priorities. This lack of time affected their ability to complete projects. Nine participants who initially enrolled in the QAP did not complete the program; primarily due to missing classes because of competing patient care priorities. The literature suggests that building successful QI capability requires adequate time to conduct QI (Fok & Wong, 2014; Goldberg et al., 2013; Parker et al., 2009; Runnacles et al., 2013; Scanlon, Alexander, et al., 2016; Schilling et al., 2010; Siverbo et al., 2014; Stille et al., 2012; Zakoscielna, Parmelee, & Lichtenstein, 2014). Without addressing this element, there is a risk that capability and ultimately capacity will be affected.

Other important gaps in the curriculum included the lack of change management concepts, use of varying modalities, validated assessment tools, and different level courses to address different skill levels. The literature reports curriculum informed by change management as an evidence-based element (Bevan, 2010; Brownlee et al., 2013; Paez, Schur, Zhao, & Lucado, 2013; Parker et al., 2009; Rask et al., 2011). Knowledge of change management theory may influence the sustainability of a project. Indeed, few participants reported changes designed to create long-term sustainability when asked what they were doing to sustain success. Most respondents reported auditing and

monitoring activities, which may lead to increased work, rather than process changes that produce reliable outcomes.

Use of varying modalities and different level courses has not surfaced in the comments for the QAP; however, the QAP faculty is considering using some “flipped classroom” techniques by requiring homework before the Academy. Additionally, physician resident training in QI concepts has begun, with prepared introductory content that can be spread to other staff. This content condenses QAP essentials into two 4-hour blocks of time, with some practice of concepts and pre course work that includes basic QI models and theories. This is designed to accelerate the numbers of staff trained to address organizational capacity.

In terms of program success, capability was operationally defined as participants gaining knowledge of QI principles and practices. Statistically significant improvements ($p = < .001$) in mean scores of self-reported proficiency in the use of (a) QI models, (b) QI tools, (c) statistical analysis, (d) managing QI processes, and (e) leading and sustaining QI were demonstrated across all three Waves for the vast majority of elements tested. Of the staff enrolled, approximately 90% were satisfied with and completed the course, including representation from front-line nurses, providers, and management staff. These findings support achievement of Kirkpatrick’s Levels 1 and 2 and are consistent with those reported in the literature (Davis et al., 2016; Kaminski et al., 2012; McNab et al., 2015; Rask et al., 2011; Riley, Parsons, Duffy, et al., 2009; Schilling et al., 2010; Wong et al., 2010).

There were particular variables that did not reach statistical significant at the $p < .001$ level. Some of these were areas that were not a focus for this course such as

ORCHID reports (the organization's electronic health record reporting tool). Others were related to the use of statistical tools, especially in Wave 1, where participants were overwhelmed learning to use MS-Excel™ simultaneously with control charts and statistical processes. Ruud et al. (2012) and Hess et al. (2013) described similar difficulty with statistical content and recommended separating this type of content into separate sessions. This was done for Wave 2 with improved course satisfaction and statistically significant improvements in pre and post scores (Table 11).

Of interest, the pre Academy means for proficiency in knowledge of QI models, tools, and statistical analysis across all Waves were closer to not at all proficient (all < 1), yet the means for knowledge of QI processes were closer to somewhat proficient (all >1). Comparing these findings to the sample demographic, where a majority of participants had either less than five years of experience or greater than 20 years of experience suggests that QI is being taught, either on the job or prior to entering the profession, but is not of sufficient depth to provide knowledge and skills for improvement. This further emphasizes the need for training in formal methods and approaches to QI if health care organizations are going to attain high reliability in their organizations as recommended by Chassin and Loeb (2013).

Capacity was operationally defined as whether participants in the QAP continue to design and implement QI projects after they graduate. Though respondents reported “somewhat” to “very confident” in conducting QI post Academy, they did not report continuing work on their projects, spreading their projects to other units, or continuing their education in QI. This is in contrast to Rask et al. (2011) who reported 68% of participants continued work on their projects post course. Brownlee et al. (2013) and

McGrath and Blike (2015) also considered continued course work as a measure of building capacity. It is not clear whether the findings in this study are due to the nature of their projects, or if other contextual factors exist.

In continuing to address organizational capacity, for Wave 2, participants reported continuing engagement in QI post graduation similar to findings by Rao et al. (2016). Engaging in additional projects suggests a level of learning transfer and behavior change consistent with Kirkpatrick's Level 3, though the types of subsequent projects are not known. These findings suggest the confidence achieved in the QAP has translated into confidence to continue conducting QI post QAP. This is a significant success for the organization as we build capacity for QI.

The qualitative responses confirmed the internalization of QI principles where participants expressed understanding of the link between the PDSAs and changes that were occurring. Interestingly, participants also reported incorporating QI principles into their daily activities, with some mentioning how the tools have been used in their personal lives.

In terms of project outcomes, diffusion of completed projects across the organization was identified in the QAP Logic Model as an intermediate goal, and the statistically significant results of more "no" responses than expected ($p = .014$) reflect a lack of diffusion, despite the statistically significant results reported for furthering education in QI ($p = .001$; Table 26). One explanation may relate to the projects chosen (they were not amenable to diffusion) or the lack of knowledge in methods of diffusion. This should be further explored in subsequent Waves of the QAP.

Paez et al. (2013) and Shortell et al. (1995) used measures of organizational culture change to evaluate internalization of behavior change in support of Kirkpatrick's Level 3 learning. Prior to implementation of the Quality Academy, this organization conducted a culture survey. A repeat culture survey, scheduled for the Fall of 2018, may provide additional insight into whether the organization's culture has changed as a result of the QAP.

Participants commented on a lack of support and time to complete their projects, even though they were completing this training with their supervisors' support. A lack of protected time to gain experience through projects was also broadly reported in the literature, suggesting a widespread lack of infrastructure across healthcare organizations (Babich et al., 2016; Daugherty et al., 2013; Fieldston et al., 2016; Fok & Wong, 2014; Gupta et al., 2014; Morgan, 2012; Runnacles et al., 2013; Siverbo et al., 2014; Sockalingam et al., 2010; Zakoscielna et al., 2014). Schilling et al. (2010) reported organizational infrastructure as a key to success. Expressing a lack of time to conduct projects also suggests that QI is not yet considered a part of everyone's job. Daniel et al. (2016) and Chassin and Loeb (2013) recommended including QI projects as part of each individual's daily work. Further exploration by this investigator should include analysis of whether specific disciplines reported lack of time at a higher ratio than others or whether the amount of time participants spent on their projects varied.

Although frontline training is emphasized as an evidence-based element, training leaders first in QI creates the context for visible organizational support (Hamilton et al., 2014; Kaminski et al., 2012; Pronovost et al., 2015; Rask et al., 2011; Rivard et al., 2013). A leader-specific program should be developed and required for all leadership across the

organization. If leaders had a better understanding of QI principles, they could model behavior and provide a level of mentoring for their front line staff to engage in QI activities.

Morganti et al. (2012) recommended using both self-report and external review of projects, which was done in this study. McNab et al. (2015) adapted the QIKAT tool to include an objective measure of projects to combine with self-reported learning, and included a percentage of completed projects subsequently published as a measure of capacity. This study used a similar tool (Appendix J). Descriptive analysis was limited to subjective assessment of metrics either met or not met by program faculty and the small sample size limits conclusions. Notwithstanding these limitations, 16 of 63 projects (25%) were specifically aimed at improving patient outcomes. Identifying and tracking clearly defined outcome metrics should be considered in the future for QAP projects.

Improving patient outcomes is the ultimate goal of any QI training program. Few studies included outcomes or achievement of Kirkpatrick's Level 4. Those that did identified Level 4 achievement as projects showing improvement (Kaminski et al., 2012; Riley, Parsons, Duffy, et al., 2009) or percent of projects published (McNab et al., 2015). Given the timeline for this project, it was not possible to fully assess improvements in patient outcomes and no projects have been published to date. However, of the 16 projects that were aimed at improving patient outcomes, 14 of 16 (88%) showed some improvement at the end of this six-month program.

Limitations

The lack of standardized measures to assess organizational capacity limits the ability to compare programs and measure capacity building within and across

organizations. Additionally, there is inherent bias in self-reported data (Polit & Beck, 2017). This paper discusses one organization's experience. The sample sizes in each Wave were small which influenced the type of statistical test used. Composite variables for domains were created to address some of the small sample sizes, thus limiting the ability to distinguish statistical significance for each element within the domain.

The construct of the survey questions created another limitation. The QAP faculty developed these questions prior to implementation of the program. In conducting the statistical analysis, the compound wording of the questions created limitations in interpretation. For example, one question asked participants to identify their level of proficiency with defining the problem statement, the goals, and scope of a project. This question would have been better as three separate questions rather than one. Decisions to revise these surveys in the future surveys should weigh the risks and benefits of better clarity versus losing historical information.

Implications for Practice

This project provided a unique chance to conduct an in-depth analysis of an existing QAP program. As a result of this study, this investigator had a rare opportunity to reflect on the QAP and recommend changes to address the gaps identified. From a practical perspective, this study provided insights into the evidence-based elements leading to successful building of capacity and capability. Subsequent Waves of the QAP should address the infrastructure deficits with senior leaders with an emphasis on opportunities of mutual benefit, specifically addressing time to conduct QI projects and ways to integrate QI into daily work.

One area of mutual benefit includes improvements in organizational culture. Several studies demonstrated statistically significant improvements in organizational culture, measuring teamwork and work engagement (Paez et al., 2013; Pearson et al., 2016; White et al., 2014; Zoutman & Ford, 2017). Zallman et al. (2013) reported improved job satisfaction when staff was involved in QI projects. Though difficult to measure, these skills translate into greater efficiency and can reduce costly rework and waste. A productive nursing workforce, armed with skills in quality improvement, can influence both the working environment and the bottom line. Providing this information to executives and leaders in this local organization may demonstrate the value of investing in and standardizing training in QI across the organization. Locally, this investigator and leaders can define specific measures of success. Further research should focus on determining relevant measures for returns on investment that can quantify both objective results (improved outcomes) and subjective results (improved morale).

Broadening the scope and looking at nursing education in general, Sherwood (2011) and Cronenwett et al. (2009) reported on the status of integrating Quality and Safety Education for Nurses (QSEN) competencies into schools of nursing. The QSEN Institute, funded by the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation in 2005, defined competencies for integration into schools of nursing. The Institute has worked since to develop faculty and integrate knowledge of quality and safety into pre-licensure and graduate nursing education. More recently, Olds and Dolansky (2017) reported that, while competencies are now included in curriculum, there remains a lack of information and research into the translation of competencies in practice. This may suggest that pre-licensure training on quality and safety concepts may need refreshing once nurses are in the workforce.

For all health care workers, this study confirms that gaps exist in QI training. As Maureen Bisognano, former Chief Executive Officer (CEO) of the IHI states, everyone's job is quality, so we must give everyone tools to do this job (Bisognano, 2013). To achieve this goal, organizations must invest in QI training. In addition to formal training sponsored by the organization, employees could be incentivized to seek professional growth opportunities in QI, such as bonuses for obtaining specialty certification in QI or allow work time to provide mentoring to new employees and students who are engaged in QI training. Organizations demonstrating support for QI and professional growth may be rewarded with a more engaged workforce, better morale, and a more efficiently run hospital.

Conclusion

This Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project identified evidence-based elements predicting successful building of capacity and capability to sustain quality initiatives. This study revealed that individuals can develop capability to conduct QI projects and organizations can build capacity through a structured educational program. Having a workforce skilled in QI methodology across all disciplines and in all areas creates an environment of continuous improvement and can improve patient care and reduce unnecessary costs. Developing a training program based on evidence-based elements provides organizations an assurance that the program will result in learning and completion of projects that improve patient outcomes. This investment in professional growth may also result in a happier and more engaged workforce, and a highly reliable organization where patients receive the best care possible with the least harm.

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APPENDIX A
TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Table A1

Table of Evidence Building Capacity and Capability

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Powell, 2008) Dissertation To examine what QI tools are used by organizations & the impact of this on outcomes	Qualitative Non-validated survey	22 people from 3 multi-hospitals systems Michigan QI leads & QI staff	Variables: QI & operations; commitment to QI; Board involvement in QI; QI outcomes	Themes: Strategic planning; business priority; regulatory; customer service	Conclusions: Opportunities exist to spread QI tools in organizations Limitations: small study, qualitative, Notes: Organizational leadership key in driving QI; staff need training in use of tools
(Filardo et al., 2009) Effectiveness of QI training in rural hospitals	Randomized control trial of formal QI training to improve core measure outcomes IV = Formal QI training DV = performance on core measures CAP & CHF using web-based benchmarking tool	47 hospitals Rural & small community in Texas Cluster randomization 22 in intervention group Excluded hospitals with previous participation in QI training; had to use web-based tool	Intervention group: Formal QI training = 2 day didactic on QI & design followed by 3 months of coaching while completing project focused on a CMS core measure (either CAP or CHF)	45 hospitals in the final analysis; 1 year later, no sig diff in core measure confounders = high staff turnover, critical access hospitals, 1 hospital in each arm (IV/control) were lost to follow up	Conclusions: Few leaders (nursing physician, administrative) attended training; Authors thought 12 months was too soon for results and planned a 24-month follow up.

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
		Groups randomized to web tool only or web tool plus QI education including content on implementing a QI initiative	Control group: No QI training Outcome measures were compulsory core measures (either CAP or CHF)	Both groups improved from baseline so no effect with QI training.	Limitations: Incomplete participation of intervention group (n = 6 completed full intervention) Note: 2 day training only- core measures only; first RCT of QI training Curriculum info QI training based on Intermountain Health Care training program 2-2 day sessions then project for next 3 months
(Riley, et. al., 2009) Training in public health sector (state-wide)	Mixed methods using Pre/Post around Kirkpatrick model & eval of projects DV: scores on surveys and project success including outcome measures from projects such as improved efficiency, cost or quality IV: Training course	38 public health departments 195 employees/managers 8 QI teams Minnesota Volunteers All training sessions not required	Measures: self-administered survey post training; pre/post survey and final projects with specific data collection fields related to projects Project “perceived overall success” measured as high, medium and low	Used Kirkpatrick’s evaluation Level 1: satisfied Level 2: confidence Level 3: future application Level 4: project outcome data shows improvement 6 of 8 projects demonstrated improvement in quality/efficiency 5 of 8 high level of overall success	Conclusions: Using distance methods for training works in public health Limitations: Voluntary participation may bias sample Note: Curriculum Info Expert facilitation Distance education Project completion Used Model for Improvement

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
				Identified what tool(s) was used in each project 10 QI methods taught Teams under-estimated time to complete project	Notes: evaluation process for QI projects (perceived level of success)
(Bevan, 2010) Building capacity and capability	Peer reviewed article	NHS England	Front line involvement Develop standard work Limited knowledge of tools – focus on managers as “role models”	Outcome should be on organizational improvements not just building capacity/capability Lack of organizational approach to teaching skills Develop 3 skills; ROI, problem solving, & innovation Involve patients & focus on sustainability	Note: focuses on Productive Ward – releasing time to care projects Incorporates change management into QI training Note: Article contains table of EB skills
(Schilling et al., 2010) To evaluate organization effectiveness in spreading QI training (part 2)	Quantitative Pre/Post survey DV: 1. 6 capabilities (leadership priority setting, systems approach to improvement, measurement capability, learning organization, improvement capability, culture)	22 medical centers in Kaiser Permanente regions	6 capabilities; “leadership priority setting, systems approach to improvement, measurement capability, learning organization, improvement capability and culture” 0-5 scale across all metrics (organization defined self-assessment)	84% projects completed Resulted in cost savings to the organization’s bottom line 61% increase in achievement of 6 capabilities Used Kirkpatrick to assess learning 100% achieved goals,	Conclusions: Keys to success included adequate time to conduct PI, strategic alignment with organization, mentoring by experienced QI advisors Front line training is important Few metrics exist for measuring organizational capacity

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
	<p>2. % PI projects completed (success defined as reaching goal set)</p> <p>3. Costs</p> <p>IV: Training</p>			Investment \$7M; financial impact of projects \$23M	<p>Limitations: Only 20% of projects had financial evaluation for ROI; not enough time for full evaluation</p> <p>Note: Kaiser's curriculum similar to Quality Academy <u>Curriculum info</u> Kaiser's improvement course</p>
<p>(Rask et al., 2011)</p> <p>EB strategies to build capacity focusing on leaders & frontline staff simultaneously</p>	<p>Quantitative Pre/post</p> <p>DV: Pre/Post survey on knowledge gain</p> <p>15 questions – non-validated tool</p> <p>6 month follow up qualitative interview</p> <p>IV: Training</p>	<p>Emory Healthcare (EMC)</p> <p>5 hospital system</p> <p>545 completed leadership & 85 completed front line</p>	<p>35% improvement post course</p> <p>27% projects had patient outcome improvements as aim</p> <p>Presentations scored on: team; aim statement & SMART goals; evidence of sustainability</p> <p>Less than 1/2 were aged enough for outcome analysis</p> <p>68% continued post course</p>	<p>Curriculum informed by change management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -visible leaders -support for QI & experience with tools; <p>on site training leads to more uptake; topics chosen by organization</p> <p>27 projects improved patient outcomes; 10 projects improved access and coordination; 7 projects improved financial performance</p> <p>86.4% fully implemented projects</p>	<p>Conclusions: Teaching top level to bottom level is successful</p> <p>Limitations: One site study; Narrow focus of initial projects limited support for org-wide resources</p> <p>Note: <u>Curriculum info:</u> Leadership course = 2 day on awareness and taxonomy Front line = 12 days over 4 months – consecutive days</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
			Some projects dropped for lack of support-49 projects total	68.4% projects continued after course Post test 81.7% answered correctly Projects scored on team functionality (3), AIM (3) statement, SMART goals,(3) systematic implementation (4) evidence for sustainability (1) total of 14 points	Lectures & small group discussions for managers; homework & activities included for front line Project required Detailed curriculum in article Note: Can offer manager training more frequently to build capacity; project scores interesting
(Schilling et al., 2011) Kaiser's experience building capacity (part IV)	Peer reviewed article	Kaiser Organization	7 building blocks of learning organizations; includes capacity; training; prioritization of improvements Balanced score card approach with operational leadership, managers and front line	Uses "Rapid Improvement Method (RIM) home grown approach using combination of IHI, Lean and care improvement teams Participant attributes: curiosity; informal leaders Organization attributes: Providing and sharing vision; recognize efforts; retrieve the voice of the customer	Authors' conclusions: challenges with ongoing training; change adoption Limitations: Not a formal study Notes: Strong framework for improvement – internal consultancy program; improvement advisors and "deep experts" available for mentoring

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Whippy et al., 2011) Continuation of Kaiser series on building capacity Use of cross functional teams to improve	Descriptive Improvement in sepsis diagnoses using rapid cycle improvement	21 Kaiser medical centers Improvement of sepsis bundle Pre/post compliance	Local teams with national help from mentor experts Rapid cycle testing	Metrics on sepsis outcomes-Lactates -From 27% baseline to 97% in 2 years early ID 35.7 to 119.4 EGDT 52% to 92% Conference calls	Conclusions: teams were able to improve sepsis metrics Limitations: only 1 measure; process measures not outcomes Piloted a "top down-bottom up" approach Notes: Project focused training opposed to training then project
(Ruud et al., 2012) Evaluation of effectiveness of a QI training program	Pre-test/Post-test design Variables: IV = Quality Academy Training course DV: Learning measured with Kirkpatrick's levels of learning (learning, behavior,	103 participants of Mayo Clinic Quality Academy 24% administrative; 78% clinical; most with <5 years of service and between 30 and 50 years old Inclusion criteria: attended quality academy	Pre/Post Quality Academy course = 80 hours didactic over 2 months Kirkpatrick's framework. Goal included learning and application. Questionnaire (Likert) format on lecture material, instructor effectiveness & course content; pretest before course start, posttest 90 days after completion; 35 questions on tools used and frequency of application of tools	Mean raw score change between pre/post was statistically significant (p < .001) for all three sessions and overall Secondary analysis = positive correlation between education level and scores Open ended questions identifying barriers & changes in use of tools	Conclusion: Consistent with other studies; positive knowledge and skill transfer post course; educational level not relevant in terms of improvement gains; worse attendance by administrative staff; Stats content difficult, so sessions broken into smaller pieces. Sessions now 6 over 1-2 days with a week to a month between sessions to allow for project completion

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					<p>Limitations: Self-selection bias in participants; internally defined training; self reported data</p> <p>Note: This format is similar to the LAC+USC Quality Academy; did not use validated tool; did not collaborate self-reports with objective data</p> <p>Curriculum info Developed similar to QAP</p>
<p>(Morganti et al., 2012)</p> <p>Purpose to figure out how to measure success in QI training programs</p>	<p>Descriptive, retrospective correlational design (2 hypothesis)</p> <p>Retrospective evaluation of interview & survey data from facilities who completed Perfecting Patient Care (PPC) University</p> <p>3 formats of PPC:</p>	<p>30 organizations post PPC training between 2006 and 2008 with at least 1 year of QI experience post training</p> <p>Stratified sampling from eligible organizations & PPC program</p> <p>Inclusion criteria: Completion of either champion program or</p>	<p>Two surveys: Key success factors and PPC skills survey</p> <p>Surveys self-developed.</p> <p>Externally rated QI success measured using self-developed tool (Likert scale) looking at improved outcomes, sustainability, & diffusion across organization and within group</p>	<p>Highest correlations between self-reported “projects successful” and “met goal”. Low correlation between self-reported and externally rated variables.</p> <p>Training dosage had statistically significant findings correlated to externally measured variables.</p>	<p>Conclusions: They recommend external objective measures rather than self-report to measure success</p> <p>Limitations: No control group, recall bias</p> <p>Notes: The lack of standards to formally evaluate QI programs impedes ability to identify “success”</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
	<p>Champion, open and customized</p> <p>Semi structured interviews and self-administered surveys</p> <p>Correlated with objective data on QI projects IV: PPC training DV: Self-reported: met goals, project successful. Externally measured: outcomes improved, sustainable monitoring, diffusion within & across units</p>	<p>either open or customized</p> <p>Exclusions: QI trainers and consultants for other training organizations</p>	<p>Measured training “dosage” using self-developed scale on number of staff trained in the organization and coaching practices.</p>	<p>Contextual factors many influence perceptions of “success”</p> <p>Self-report and external measurement will lead to different results.</p> <p>Hypothesis 1: Perceived measures of success > externally measured success –accepted</p> <p>Hypothesis 2: Differences between self-report and QI training on externally measured variables – accepted</p> <p>Project success factors: leadership involvement; empowerment; team effectiveness; end user involvement; monitoring performance</p>	<p>across training programs.</p> <p>Note: Good for project to consider external measures of “success”.</p> <p>Capacity using both self-report and external review of project</p> <p>Note: Similar to Quality Academy</p> <p>Curriculum info Self-developed PPC</p>
<p>(Joly, Booth, Shaler, & Conway, 2012)</p> <p>Building capacity using QI collaboratives</p>	<p>Qualitative</p> <p>Multi-site case study methodology</p> <p>Measured constructs of time to implement a</p>	<p>16 states participating in an IHI collaborative for public health over a 2 year time frame</p> <p>Kansas, Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Florida,</p>	<p>Thematic coding of interviews with sub-coding</p>	<p>Relevant findings included need for planning, qualified faculty, senior leader support, standard improvement model, clear roles and responsibilities,</p>	<p>Conclusion: use of tools should be linked to projects and collaboratives are just one part of a strategy to build capacity</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
	collaborative, expert faculty, type of technical assistance needed, ensuring organizational support to ensure spread of QI Phone interviews, interpretive phenomenological analysis	Michigan, Minnesota, Missouri, Montana, New Hampshire, New Jersey, Oklahoma, South Carolina, Washington and Wisconsin		resources to make changes, motivation of staff Process was not sustainable post collaborative due to lack of knowledge and difficulty understanding QI tools	Limitations: Could not evaluate Q projects – no standard measures Notes: Statewide collaboratives a little different from organization-run QI, but informs the organizational constructs for QI
(Kaminski et al., 2012) To evaluate success of facility designed course	Pre/Post Survey on learning, application, impact DV: Knowledge of 5 quality improvement topics; changes in behavior, project completed with measureable results & continued participation in QI IV: I ² S ² = Facility designed course	Cincinnati Children's Hospital –Urban pediatric academic hospital 279 participants since 2009; 106 clinical & 79 administrative	I ² S ² course operational definition: Based on Kolb's theory of experiential learning Training = 2 days/month for 6 months mixed book, lecture, interactive w/case studies QI self-assessment survey administered prior to course and on the last day of the course DVs measured using self-developed questionnaires and analysis of project results (for project completion & measurable results)	82% response rate. Statistically significant gains in knowledge framed with Kirkpatrick level 2 (participant learning) (p<0.0001) Kirkpatrick level 3 (change in behavior); 13% published results of project; 50% completed projects Kirkpatrick level 4 (project results) 85% projects had measurable improvements	Conclusions: Leaders needed same in-depth training as participants Course expectations include QI projects and leadership; project selection critical. 1:1 coaching through project & regular project review is key Limitations: One site study, Note: Good study to evaluate QI training program using Kirkpatrick model;

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					<u>Curriculum info</u> Self-designed course similar to QAP
(Rivard et al., 2013) What is QI success?	Qualitative Exploratory comparison Premise: QI leads to knowledge, knowledge leads to change and change leads to improved outcomes	4 VA hospitals Purposive sampling of hospitals that had good outcome data versus bad outcome data 63 staff interviews	Used patient safety indicators as performance benchmark	Defined project level learning as whether the project was successful Defined program level learning as structural to QI program Programs identified lack of MD involvement and lack of leadership visibility as challenges	Conclusions: Project level versus program level outcomes are different Limitations: case study method; used patient safety indicators which may not be best measure Note: Though focused on QI programs –not just training- this reiterates need for strong leadership support for structural components of QI – building knowledge and skills
(Runnacles et al., 2013) MD's need skills in QI	Descriptive study of "Enabling doctors in Quality Improvement and Patient Safety" (EQUIP) program Pre/Post evaluation	London Children's hospital 39 residents pre and 22 residents post program	Self-designed survey on knowledge & skills in QI Satisfaction with course; success of project (e.g. improved outcomes); thematic	Pre/post knowledge improved – participants report increased confidence Residents thought projects improved patient outcomes Key success factors: structured program with	Conclusions: Teaching QI empowers providers to make changes; skills are transferrable Limitations: One site Notes: Used 7 slides for sharing program:

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
			evaluation of described success vs barriers	<p>project; peer support; executive support; mentoring; manager engagement; expert advice; time; properly scoped project</p> <p>Barriers: time; lack of support; no mentoring; organization doesn't want change</p>	<p>problem, driver diagram, SMART aim, measurements, and next steps</p> <p>Curriculum Info MD resident completes project with mentored support 3 levels. Level 1 = 1 hr. workshop; level 2 = 2 days over 6 months & project, with mentor Level 3 = spreading results</p>
(Hamilton et al., 2014)	<p>Qualitative content analysis</p> <p>Mixed methods Pre/Post categorization on QI capacity (per framework)</p> <p>Analyzed units with positive/negative capacity pre/post</p> <p>Post implementation of Releasing Time to Care (RTC)</p>	<p>Purposive sampling in 8 nursing units in Canada to choose 2 units for analysis</p> <p>4-7 participants per unit using snowball</p> <p>Semi-structured interviews</p>	<p>Codes and mostly deductive thematic evaluation matched to framework</p> <p>Organizing quality framework = 6 domains Structural, political, cultural, educational, emotional, physical/technical</p>	<p>Improved QI capacity on units with prior experience in QI</p> <p>Positive units more easily adapted QI to work culture</p> <p>Weaker unit-not successful, not motivated – did it because they had to</p>	<p>Conclusions: RTC shows promise in supported organization; front line ownership key</p> <p>Limitations: small sample; focus on 2 units</p> <p>Note: Speaks to organizational support and leadership as a contextual factor for success</p>
(Kaminksi et al., 2014)	Descriptive study teaching QI tools using	Cincinnati children's hospital	Basic course = 6 half days; intermediate	Developed QI leaders first, then focused on frontline,	Conclusion: QI training leads to use of QI tools;

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
	<p>rapid cycle improvements Variables included number of staff trained over 2 year period in various modalities, including online, collaborative and I²S² course</p>	<p>Pediatric Academic Center</p>	<p>course = 6 half days and project with coach, Advanced = 4 2 day sessions and 4 90 min calls with project Advanced Leadership is 7 half day sessions and work between session, post doc program is a 3 year curriculum</p>	<p>Inter-professional projects, with a coach to develop critical mass of capable individuals trained Leadership support critical The culture created by the numbers of staff trained in QI led to more capacity to improve. Critical mass required to grow QI capacity</p>	<p>inter-professional = more robust improvements Limitation: One training program Notes: Authors defined capacity and capability similarly and in terms of a macro, meso, and micro system for QI Detailed curriculum included in article Good discussion on micro/meso/macro levels of training with tools to cover at each level Good roadmap to designing a robust QI training program</p>
<p>(Kislov et al., 2014) Developing capability and capacity</p>	<p>Descriptive study Variables: 1st to 3rd order capabilities similar to Kirkpatrick levels of learning</p>	<p>UK health system</p>	<p>Developing ability to translate improvements or knowledge from one area to another</p>	<p>Organizations should look to develop capacity rather than build capacity All knowledge acquisition is iterative with active participation</p>	<p>Conclusion: Authors note that experience based learning is key; focus away from what topics to how are skills used</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
				Learning organizations: individual versus group learning; group learning to organizational learning; organizational learning to individual learning	Limitations: descriptive study Notes: defined different levels of learning in organizations to build capacity
(McKeever & Rider, 2014) Capacity in health departments	Descriptive study of a coaching model	30 public health sites 85 coaches trained	Survey of coaching effectiveness (response rate of 46%) QI projects completed	80% strongly agreed that coaching was effective, self-reported increases in use of QI tools and techniques	Conclusions: Authors noted that training should be standardized for coaches, including setting expectations
(Adams et al., 2015) Sustaining QI initiatives	Descriptive study vs peer reviewed article looking at use of consultative teams to drive improvement Variables: increase ID of sepsis, implement treatment and monitor	21 Kaiser hospitals OCG members act as consultants	Sepsis measures Developed a "playbook"	Improved performance through use of consultative teams and hospital staff working collaboratively	Limitations: Limited study Notes: Key points: facilitation model works well; Mentorship with local teams; front line teams work best
(Lee et al., 2015) Spreading EPIQ program to other NICUS	Prospective pre/ post Control & experimental group IV: training DV: incidence of bronco pulmonary dysplasia, nosocomial infection	Voluntary 19 NICUs Canada 8 in control group (received practice guidelines without QI training) 11 in intervention group (received practice	Collaborative model to share across NICUs Measured incidence of infection & bronco pulmonary dysplasia	Statistically significant downward trend in outcome indicators in the intervention group compared to baseline	Conclusions: Merely sharing guidelines without QI work won't change practice Limitations: Only 1 unit, hospital Notes: Speaks to cultural change that

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
		<p>guidelines with QI training)</p> <p>5812 infants <32 weeks admitted to 19 units over 2 years</p>			<p>happens with QI training</p> <p>Curriculum info Evidence-based practices for improving quality –tailored to sites 2 day train the trainer on QI for 2 team members from each of the NICUs; team building plus QI tools; communication; change management</p> <p>Note: the process of forming teams and doing changes has an impact on results; suggests other contextual factors associated with improvements post training</p>
<p>(McGrath & Blike, 2015)</p> <p>Building capacity through education</p>	<p>Descriptive study on development of organization-wide QI training</p> <p>Variables: # Staff trained @ each skill level (basic,</p>	<p>Level 1 hospital in New Hampshire Several hospitals and health centers including level 1 trauma center</p>	<p>Level of training completed</p> <p>Numbers of staff completing projects</p> <p>Improvement projects completed</p>	<p>Organization-wide capacity built with over 10,000 staff trained in 20 months. Levels of training from white belt to green belt Trained across</p>	<p>Conclusion: Authors recommend an accountability structure with appropriate goal setting</p> <p>Limitations: One study site</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
	intermediate, advanced and expert) # Improvement projects Total ROI		ROI total	Realistic goal setting is necessary for success 37% projects completed; 49% continued post training; Calculated ROI pre/post project ROI 2.5 times investment in training	Notes: Huge investment in time and capital for training resources; 124 improvement projects across organization, good info on tracking Curriculum info: DMAIC framework used, self-developed Basic = 1-2 hrs. Intermediate = 16 hrs. + project participation Advanced = 40 hours plus project Expert 80-120 hours plus practicum
(McNab et al., 2015) Standardize QI training for residents	Mixed methods Pre/post evaluations of knowledge and confidence in QI Variables: Project completion rate, knowledge gain, publication success	20 volunteer medical residents in Scotland	QIPAT 7 = validated tool to measure projects Thematic assessment of 1:1 interviews Adapted QIKAT used at pre/post training day and end of training and 4 months	Used logic model and Kirkpatrick's model for evaluation Level 1 – training successful Level 2&3 confidence-improved post training; projects scored 75% appropriate; 95% used tools appropriately Level 4: completed projects 43%; 17% published	Curriculum info: Training plus project & mentoring 1 day over 3 months Included QI, teamwork, leadership, systems thinking – specifics not described Author's concluded mentoring important; lack of skills precludes ability to conduct PI;

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					<p>capability & capacity hindered by lack of standardized approaches to QI Limitations: small sample and incomplete projects</p> <p>Note: Evaluation method similar to QAP; suggested counting number of PDSA's as a measure of performance <u>Curriculum info:</u> Training plus project & mentoring 1 day over 3 months Included QI, teamwork, leadership, systems thinking – specifics not described</p>
(Moore & Stichler, 2015) QI for nurses	Peer reviewed article	Magnet Hospital Short stay unit	Knowles adult learning Kirkpatrick's levels of knowledge Change management and DMAIC 7 step framework for evidence-based care	Use QI tools to present data, develop metrics and aims, DMAIC model to improve Improved compliance with line tracing, patient identification, hand hygiene, falls, reduced caregiver stress,	Conclusion: Project was well received, culture change identified – no measures Limitations: not a study, time pressures to do QI Note <u>Curriculum info:</u>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					Didactic, 1:1 mentoring, group discussions with advanced practice staff
(Pronovost et al., 2015) What are infrastructure needs for QI	Peer reviewed article Compliance on core measures 7 process measures 95% compliance	2 academic medical centers and 3 community hospitals	Percent of eligible patients process measures at 95% compliant	>96% compliance achieved on 6/7 measures over 2 year period Organizational infrastructure = teams trained in QI, frontline engagement, leadership & transparency	Conclusion: governing body sets accountability for QI Limitations: Not a study Note: identifies elements for organizational success
(Pearson et al., 2016) Evaluation of frontline staff ability to conduct PI	Observational mixed methods time series TCAB implementation methodology using front line nursing staff Variables: teamwork, improved outcomes	52 healthcare organizations in New Jersey; 50 acute care, 1 children's rehab and 1 home health organization 1 med/surgical nursing unit at each site Mean of 34 beds	4 research questions related to implementation of TCAB & improvements resulting from TCAB several different surveys used, including teamwork assessment Also collected unit level falls, HAPU, LOS and HCAPHS	98% implemented TCAB Statistically significant improvements in teamwork and outcomes Frontline nurses would participate in more TCAB initiatives Capacity building in that nurses had confidence and skills to conduct other projects Can result in organization culture changes	Conclusions: Includes a mentoring model with expert coaches and a collaboration model with multiple organizations contributing to learning Limitations: No control; self-selected sample Notes: QI teams led by unit staff not QI staff; managers need to give time to frontline staff for this work Curriculum: used Model for Improvement and brainstorming

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					Included didactics, webinars, leadership training
(Daniel et al., 2016) Using multiple projects to build capacity	Descriptive study How do you conduct QI training?	ICU in Glasgow Royal Infirmary	30 minutes added to grand rounds to provide didactic content Taught through 4 projects Run charts developed for each project and reviewed at the meeting	Using the IHI project assessment scale (1-5) all projects reached 4.5, goal was to achieve high reliability on project results;	Author's conclusions: Avoid trying to improve too many projects at once Limitations: small scale Notes: This project built QI capability with individuals as part of their usual work
(Rao et al., 2016) Training review of practicing physicians (Partners Clinical Improvement Leadership Program)	Quantitative Pre & post scores on self-reported questions 6 month post completion survey Self-reported understanding of QI Self-reported sustained QI	239 teams of 516 individuals of practicing clinicians Boston health care system	IHI knowledge self-assessment tool used Final presentation elements: Problem statement, team members, process map, cause and effect diagram, data, voice of the patient, aim statement, measures, baseline data, prioritization matrix, PDSA cycles, Post data, conclusions and next steps (rather complex)	66% continued working on projects; 28% published findings; 62% started another project; 64% taught to others and 84% recommended the course to a colleague. Recommendations to improve = more faculty; online and tiered courses; post grad work to sustain improvements Benefits of internally developed programs defined as ability to modify curriculum based on the local context & growing faculty members	Curriculum info 6 days interdisciplinary teams; didactic, activities, case studies, final presentation over 4 months – split into 1-2 day sessions Conclusions: Graduates can serve as coaches for the next session; locally developed program is cost-effective Limitations – course too short for outcome measures

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					Notes: Detailed curriculum included in article
(Scanlon, Alexander, et al., 2016) Does AF4Q work? Community based realignment of resources to improve the health of a community	Longitudinal mixed methods evaluation 144 measures of triple aim in communities using AF4Q and control group	16 grantees for the Aligning Forces for Quality (AF4Q) Local health communities	Used logic model as framework for evaluating program; Focus on alliances rather than QI training	No differences found between AF4Q and control; some smaller successes identified Lessons learned: visionary leadership key, stakeholder engagement, assumptions around engagement, patient engagement desirable, announcing goals publicly without stakeholders can influence outcomes	Conclusions: Failures linked to lack of resources and community leadership Limitations: variations in application of program Note: suggests importance of context in programs
(Vackerberg et al., 2016) Building capacity with coaches	Qualitative Case Study design using focus groups Variables: Elements essential for coaching, experiences on training and what it is like to be an Esther coach	The Esther Network (municipalities, a hospital, primary and private providers publicly funded in Sweden) Recruited 17 coaches who had had training and completed an improvement project	Inductive content analysis Will, ideas and execution critical elements for sustainability	Freedom to choose their own projects was a plus, Use of tools too rigid, Patient involvement critical, Senior leadership critical, improvement is dynamic, communication skills also important	Conclusions: Including the customer on the team improves outcomes Limitations: One site, small sample Notes: training internal coaches, informed by patients and armed with tools, working on projects they pick will lead to sustainable organizational changes.

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Fieldston et al., 2016) Using innovation units to conduct QI	Descriptive study Variables: # improvement ideas, #PSDA cycles, # projects spread to other units	Children's Hospital of Philadelphia 2 Med/Surgical units 20-22 beds general pediatric hematology and medically complex patients	Training included IHI open school modules Standardized template developed for each PDSA cycle Sustainability defined as completing additional projects	170 staff and 70 MDs attended kickoffs 150 ideas generated within 2 months Pilot year each unit selected up to 7 projects and completed >40 tests of change Some elements of all projects successful Senior leadership support critical to success Incorporating QI into job descriptions and providing protected time improves QI activity participation	Conclusions: Training frontline staff to lead QI in "innovation unit" was successful and sustainable Limitations: data collection limited; measuring culture difficult Note: Article contains good prioritization matrix for projects Would have been interesting to have one of the units a control unit Curriculum info: IHI Open school Collectively staff completed >160 hours of training Staff led improvements can gain more momentum than top down requirements

Notes: AF4Q = Aligning Forces for Quality, CAP = Community Acquired Pneumonia, CHF = Congestive heart failure, DMAIC = design, measure, analyze, improve, control, DV = dependent variable, EPIC = evidence-based practice for improving quality, IV = independent variable, HAPU = Hospital Acquired

Pressure Ulcer, HCAPHS = Healthcare consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems, LOS = length of stay, LPI = leadership practices inventory, NICU = neonatal intensive care unit, PDSA = Plan, do, study, act, PPC = Perfecting Patient Care, QAP = Quality Academy Program, QI = Quality Improvement, ROI = return on investment, TCAB = Transforming Care at the Bedside.

Table A2

Table of Evidence for Organizational Success

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Shortell et al., 1995) Organizational culture & QI	Cross sectional Variables: Organization culture Clinical efficiency Developed scales for culture and QI Used CQI/TQM approach	61 hospitals across U.S. N = 7000 72% response rate 58 systems and 3 free standing 35% teaching	Baldrige QI implementation tool with 6 scales (leadership, information & analysis, HR utilization, empowerment, quality management, strategic planning Culture assessed by 20 question validated tool (n = 7337) 72% response rate; National survey of hospital quality efforts tool to assess HR and patient outcomes LOS for core measures & charges for core measures	CQI = lower LOS & lower charges, Larger hospital = lower culture of teamwork Risk taking = organizational attribute for success QI leads to better outcomes Large hospitals = ↓efficiency (hierarchical culture) Success elements: just in time training, decentralized control, front line empowerment,	Conclusions: Organizational culture must be flexible and able to embrace change Limitations on single point in time measures for culture, outcome, and charges. Note: Key point is hospital culture must support QI
(Bobiak et al., 2009) Psychometrics on tool to measure capacity for change	Instrument reliability study to test for organizational culture	Primary care practices (opposed to hospitals) 3 health care systems in northeast Ohio	Construct: Capacity for change Includes: motivations, external influences,	Identified elements that assess organizational capacity for change	Conclusions: Tool to measure organizational readiness to change

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
			resources and options for change Organization attributes = leadership, communication, trust and leadership	Elements: Degree of conflict, shared vision, supportive work environment, acceptance of change, strategic thinking, flexibility, focused change	Limitations: Too little is known about capacity to change; more testing of tool is needed Note: useful for elements for organization success
(Apekey et al., 2011) To determine relationships between leadership, culture and use of QI tools	Descriptive correlational study Mailed questionnaires (4 parts: background info, leadership behavior, culture of innovation and QI methods) Variables: Leadership behavior Culture of innovation QI tool usage	102 QI leads in medical practices throughout the National Health Service (NHS) (England's health system) Inclusion criteria: All medical practices in county of interest. Exclusion criteria: none	Questionnaires: Leadership behavior self-perception of 12 items derived from LPI leadership tool QI tool usage using internally developed tool with Likert scale on use of 22 QI tools	62% response rate No demographic differences in non-responders More training practices responded (p = 0.001) Limited use of leadership behaviors & QI tools Positive correlation leadership & culture of innovation R = 0.57; P < 0.001	Conclusion: Claims of positive culture for innovation not shown; Limited use of QI tools Limited leadership behaviors Limitations: Limited sample size, self-reports Note: Authors reflected on the need for formal QI training as evidenced by responses to use of QI tools. Leadership key Note: Some questions from tool might be useful for inclusion in pre/post survey for quality academy Curriculum info

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Estrada, et al., 2012) Leadership in Quality	Descriptive study	VA National Scholars program	Attainment of grants, completion of projects, advanced training	106 graduates, 42 projects, 29 teaching activities, 44 presentations, 36 publications, 6 grants funded and 2 awards	<p>Culture for improvement instrument NHS designed internally to measure degree innovation along 7 dimensions (risk, resources, information, targets, tools, reward, relationships)</p> <p>Conclusion: Interprofessional training creates strong organizations and leaders</p> <p>Limitations: descriptive study only, no data included</p> <p>Notes: Collected info on scholarship post training as well – good to include in QAP</p> <p>Curriculum info Local curriculum, 25/yr teleconferences 3/yr face to face Fellows project Clinical skills</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Blake et al., 2012) Perception of training & value of investment in QI	Qualitative study Semi-structured interviews one year post training Pre/post course content Grounded theory	Emory HealthCare (EHC) 545 senior leaders (1/4 nurses)	33 questions measuring QI experience, perception, objectives, confidence, knowledge, impact and organizational support Skills = aim statements, metric selection, flow charting, cause/effect diagrams, pareto, PDSAs	Varying levels of pre-course experience – Knowledge increased post course surveys 2.5 to 4.1 across all domains Preferred case based learning and lectures over group project QI expert involvement was needed EHC increased in UHC ranking from 45 th to 10 th based on organizational investment in QI	Conclusions: Training is good investment design courses consistent with QI experience pre-course to improve outcome Limitations: Self-selection bias, recall bias, Notes: Advise on curriculum to include QI vocabulary, adapt to learning styles of participants, provide guidance for projects, provide pre-training
(Nembhard, 2012) Attributes of learning collaboratives	Cross sectional analysis of learning collaboratives Self-administered surveys and semi-structured phone interviews Review of performance data Low performers High performers	53 teams participating in IHI collaboratives from US and Canada (217 respondents)	Perceptions of features in collaboratives 4 control variables: membership in other collaboratives; prior collaboratives, teaching status	Identified 6 most important elements: faculty; frontline staff inclusion; toolkit, PDSA cycles, learning sessions and extranet with statistically significant differences in all but extranet between low and high performers Less important: lit review, site visits, list serves, monthly conference calls, team conference calls	Conclusions: Participation in collaboratives signals prioritization of QI & focus on training to staff Limitations Limited to use of collaboratives Notes: Speaks to sharing of info as QI tool

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
				Used to implement evidence base practice	Curriculum info Though not QI training, includes methodology of training in the context of the collaborative, heavy focus on team interaction
(Morganti et al., 2014) Organization-wide QI evaluation	Retrospective-Descriptive Variables: Knowledge gained and improvements in quality Survey on implementation success DV: composite success in QI IV: training	Pittsburgh Regional Health Initiative 93 organizations 3 training types 29 organization interviews	Importance of training Total training dosage Competencies Cultural achievement Organizational infrastructure and capacity Implementation process effectiveness External QI success measures: improved outcome, sustainable monitoring, diffusion of QI within group and across organization	4/5 for training importance Higher scores for outcomes lower scores for diffusion measures Organization infrastructure correlated to improved competency Diffusion across the organization lower Training dosage correlated with success Organizational success factors: culture of improvement; learning organization; applying standard work	Conclusions: First study to look at success of implementing more QI post training (Level 3 & 4 of Kirkpatrick) Limitations: Only for organizations post QI training & no control group Notes: Curriculum Info: Lean methodology Limitations: small sample, retrospective review and bias, Supports organizational investment in QI
(White et al., 2014)	Quantitative	180 groups for productive ward	(Utrecht Work Engagement Scale	Statistically significant differences on work	Conclusion: work engagement predicts

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
QI training leads to culture of improvement	IV: Productive Ward initiative (QI training) DV: Scores on work engagement scale	158 controls Ireland 7 hospitals and a match control set Stratified sampling from wards	(UWES) = validated tool to measure engagement Productive ward = QI training to a) increase time at pt. bedside, b) improve satisfaction and c) change wards structurally to realize efficiencies (e.g. Lean)	engagement between experimental and control group	organization willingness to learn –embrace QI and improve outcomes Limitations in sampling Note: identifies importance of a structured QI training program to engage staff & drive improvement
(Callahan, 2015) Dissertation on QI knowledge transfer	Quantitative	198 active-duty military and non-military staff of a procurement organization	Relationship between QI and organizational learning	Knowledge transfer Organizational implementation of QI Self-developed survey Findings: attributes of change readiness and organizational culture key	Conclusion: Correlation between QI & Org learning & change management Limitations: Small response rate Note: adds to information on contextual factors of organizational culture and QI
(Babich et al., 2016) What organizational strategies are successful?	Mixed methods Survey data and qualitative data IV = grant focus (project, training or organization)	29 health care organizations Veteran's Admin who rec'd grants to build QI capacity	Improvement capability Organizational learning Content analysis Project = focused on improving in one project area Training = only training	Developing organizational capacity for QI – e.g. infrastructure, support, is more effective than training Findings: Organization focus significantly higher than others; for score	Conclusions: training with or without project focus doesn't build capacity as well as organizational infrastructure and strategy embraced by front line

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
	DV = qualitative interview data & employee survey data		<p>Organization = added infrastructure for QI</p> <p>Qualitative data analyzed quantitatively</p> <p>Learning Organization Survey (LOS) = validated instrument administered nationally to 15% of VA employees; measures learning environment, experimentation, training, leadership, knowledge acquisition & performance monitoring (5 point Likert)</p> <p>QI survey = same population 6 item Likert on QI activity</p>	changes on survey; organization focused was statistically higher than others	<p>Limitations: Each group started with a different level of QI, so results interpreted w/caution; only VA facilities</p> <p>Note: speaks to infrastructure building while training and doing projects</p>
<p>Zoutman and Ford (2017)</p> <p>Factors associated with successful QI Implementation</p>	<p>Quantitative</p> <p>Pre/Post Survey</p> <p>DV: Achieve/sustain QI goals, patient care and patient safety ratings</p> <p>IV: Staff engagement, training, compensation,</p>	<p>Acute Care Hospital CEOs in Canada; self-developed survey 125 hospitals, 47 survey responses (37%)</p>	<p>Multiple regression Factors: formal QI training, ability to collect data, all employees involved, MD engagement</p>	<p>Multiple regression: (1) nurses active involvement & physician engagement = ↑ patient care (2) MD involved & engaged = ↑ patient safety</p> <p>Factors for success: nurse & MD engagement</p>	<p>Conclusions: suggest employing strategies to increase MD engagement</p> <p>Limitations: Self-reported survey and low response rate; did not include other important factors in analysis (e.g.,</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					org leadership, champions, data collection & analysis Notes: is it lack of training that limits engagement?

Notes: CQI/TQM = continuous quality improvement/total quality management, EHC = Emory HealthCare, HR = human resources, LOS = length of stay, LPI = Leadership Performance Inventory, NHS = National health Service, QI = Quality Improvement, UHC = University Health System Consortium, UWES = Utrecht Work Engagement Scale, VA = Veteran's Administration,

Table A3

Table of Evidence for Participant's Success

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Watts et al., 2009) Physician experiences w/QI training	Qualitative grounded theory Using constant comparative methods	24 trainees Department of Medicine Case Western Reserve University	Thematic evaluation Questions: how has QI been successful or counterproductive Who rec'd the best care, why? Who was challenging, why?	Themes: Unintended consequences of QI included, more work, gaming, discouraged reflection, QI success included improved processes, decreased errors, best practices	Conclusion: Themes suggest ways to address physician buy in Limitations: small sample only physicians in one specialty Notes: <u>Curriculum Info</u> Concepts of QI, chart review, audits on QI, reading provided; 2 nd session reflection on abstraction tools Note: speaks to context in inviting participants to training
(Parker et al., 2009) Who does QI	Qualitative Semi-structured Content analysis	Veteran's Health Admin 21 regional networks participating in TIDES program (translating initiatives for depression into effective solutions) N = 44 frontline staff	QI value at the front line	Local participation in QI valued; expert QI assistance needed; prefer face to face communication; desired info on program quality and burden; beliefs about change; managers want data; qualitative or	Conclusions: Participation in QI requires organization to provide adequate time to do this Limitations: Limited to staff, didn't include patients, small study

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
		N = 5 administrators N = 19 managers Total 68 interviews		quantitative data works; QI experts not the best for leading; group meetings best	Notes: Leadership support key Change management skills required Important to address context, workload issues with staff in QI Supports frontline involvement in QI
(Daugherty et al., 2013) Frontline experience with QI	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews (38 minutes on average) Pre/Post skills assessment	Emory Healthcare 22 staff post training Purposive sampling N = 16 managers/supervisors	32 questions covering 7 domains background, curriculum, group project, safety culture, team dynamics, leadership involvement, leadership endorsement	Themes: Course improved QI understanding; hands on experience good, supervisor support required, mentors key, project necessary for practice, length of course problematic, course led to more QI, Improved pre/post skills	Conclusions: Findings suggest helpful info for training courses Limitations: Selection & recall bias Notes: <u>Curriculum Info</u> 12 day course over 4 months, 3 sessions, Leadership key Time to complete projects key Recommended training materials in advance, QI refreshers Qualitative Questions included in article

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Djukic, Kovner, Brewer, Fatehi, & Seltzer, 2013) On the job QI training for RNs	Descriptive cross sectional Mixed mode survey Variables: preparation & participation of new RN's to work site QI training	RN's in 15 states N = 3,216 surveys sent N = 1,765 returned (57% response rate) After exclusions n = 400	QSEN used to inform survey questions	RN's reported preparedness with QI tools and methodologies, but lacked training in starting or implementing QI projects & using QI tools	Conclusion: Nurse educators should assess knowledge gaps and fill them for new nurses Limitations: Limited to new nurses Notes: Supports provision of QI training for RNs
(Neeman, Ranji, & Sehgal, 2012) Trainee participation in QI	Descriptive	Department of Medicine at UC San Francisco 29 teams (residents, fellows, med students and non-physician clinicians and staff) N = 136	Implement QI projects	24 QI projects completed	Conclusions: Competition between teams accelerated learning Limitations: Small group Notes: Authors did not address improvement on projects, just names of projects, would have been more useful to discuss process more
(Morgan, 2012) Use of mentoring	Quasi-experimental pre/post intervention Pilot study Barriers assessment	Setting: 216 bed community hospital in southeast USA N = 15	Pressure ulcer improvement was underlying project	After providing education on evidence-based practices performance improved and HAPU decreased. Barriers: Time, MD cooperation, understanding	Conclusions: Examined use of EBP and barriers to adoption using QI Limitations: small sample

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
				of QI tools, statistics, no authority,	Note: Information translatable to training in QI
(Goldberg et al., 2013) Primary care practices and QI	Qualitative case study methodology Grounded theory	N = 51 primary care providers in Virginia Purposive sampling to obtain distinct participants	Evaluation of practice group not individuals Used structural contingency theory to explain findings	Barriers included time, resources, knowledge & organizational culture Mandatory versus deciding what to measure on their own PCMH models were better aligned with improvement efforts Knowledge of change management, work pressures were barriers	Conclusions: Alignment of incentives and management support keys to success Limitations: Small sample of MDs in family practice Notes: Offers info on contextual factors
(Hess et al., 2013) Instrument for resident confidence in QI	Psychometric for Quality Improvement Confidence Instrument measuring skill in QI	N = 732 Internal Med residents from 42 training programs in US	6 domains: define the issue; build a team, define the problem; choose a target; test change; spread improvements	Testing showed low ratings for testing change (related to data analysis and use of tools for data display and choosing a target (evaluating interventions & basic QI skills) Factor analysis $r = .86$	Conclusions: Tools measuring confidence can be used pre/post to assess training Limitations: Not used to assess pre/post in this study Notes: Would be interesting to use as pre/post for QI evaluation or for pre-

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					evaluation to choose participants Authors' recommend using tool to compare confidence and competency with defined project
(Jefferis, Lo, et al., 2013) What are perceptions of line staff?	Qualitative	500 bed acute care in Canada 13 participants Staff involved CUE-QI (care utilizing evidence quality improvement)	Coding schema collected themes	Three themes: improving care collaboratively; driving QI – pride in work (professional development); overcoming challenges (especially with engagement of team) Identified common constraints including time to conduct project work	Conclusion: Protected time is needed to do QI Limitations: Small sample Notes: Curriculum info: Didactic, experiential, project over 6 months with mentors; pre-work included review of best practice & evidence
(Paez et al., 2013) QI in rural hospitals	Descriptive survey Variables: safety culture Resources, barriers and leadership engagement for QI	N = 300 nurse execs 530 Rural hospitals 11 states associated with AHRQ & HCUP data project	Self-developed survey on safety culture, adequacy of QI resources, barriers to QI and nurse leadership behavior Questions including support for QI training, access to QI training,	57% response rate 10% paid for training 30-40% QI implementation training 30% insufficient training	Conclusions: Informs need to incorporate change management into QI training Limitations: setting, sample Notes: Recommends more focus on QI training

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Zallman et al., 2013) Provider's perspective on QI capacity	Descriptive Variables: Interest in QI Training in QI Job satisfaction Barriers	Safety net hospital providers in Boston 260 surveyed (136 responses -52%) 18 primary care practices	4 point Likert scale	78% interested 63% no training 95% more satisfied if they were involved 65% barrier was time	Conclusion: Addressed barriers to increasing QI knowledge Limitations: Low response rate to survey Note: speaks to time needed for QI
(Longenecker & Longenecker, 2014) Why improvement fails	Qualitative Focus group (4 person)	167 frontline leaders 4 Midwest hospitals 42 focus groups Top 10 list from each group	Focused discussion on failures	Top ten: poor planning; no buy-in; poor leadership; unrealistic plan; poor communication; no urgency for change; poor teamwork; no measurement strategy; unclear goal; no time	Conclusion: Supports inclusion of change management principles into QI Limitations: small sample Note: typical issues for lack of success – modeled after Kotter's 8 steps of change
(Zakoscielna et al., 2014)	Cross sectional on-line survey w/quantitative and qualitative questions on QI and training needs	N = 289 leadership staff Veteran's Nursing Homes	Assessed use of minimal data set on nursing home QI, QI training	43% response rate Themes: lack of training, involvement, interest, time, motivation and understanding of value of process 35% recommended QI training	Conclusion: lack of education on value of QI and QI training Limitations: specific to one tool used in skilled nursing Note: Informs need for staff understanding of their roles in QI and

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					training to support the roles
(Siverbo et al., 2014) To evaluate changes in attitude r/t QI training	Pre/post survey Attitudes in doing QI work Variables measured: Time for improvements, criteria for improvements, working differently, Thinking differently, improvement = fun	443 participants at a University Hospital in Sweden who attended a 2 day course on QI Inclusion criteria: Management staff who attended training; training developed by Swedish hospital using methodology (similar to PDSA)	Questionnaire developed by Sahlgrenska University Hospital; 8 questions Prior to training & 6 months post training Attitudes towards QI measuring variables of interest	All: P = 0.0008 for criteria to evaluate change P = 0.0547 for enough time for QI No significant finding that improvement work is fun	Conclusion: Seasoned managers less supportive of QI than new managers, may need different type of training Limitations: data from first questionnaire not tracked, so some was lost. Managers may need different training; study measured only attitudes Note: training used natural work groups who practice problem solving in the workshops. Groups had better understanding of time commitment for QI after training
(Masters, 2015) Use of mentors in QI training	Peer reviewed article	Memorial Hermann 1047 bed academic hospital in Texas	Use of 6 sigma & DMAIC, Evaluation post training	100 physicians completed 7 month program Mentor builds confidence	Conclusion: QI requires training plus practical experience; assigned mentors accelerate the learning Limitations: Not a study

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
				<p>Mentors should be experts with enough time to assist in skill enhancement.</p> <p>Program participants conducted subsequent QI projects and took on leadership roles (e.g. built capacity)</p>	<p>Notes: <u>Curriculum info:</u> 6 classes, starting with developing project charter, meetings with mentor between each class and after final class; final is project presentation with post implementation data</p>
(Phillips et al., 2016) Front line engagement	Descriptive study Building engagement In everyday work	336 bed hospital in Virginia Level 1 stroke center, 23,000 ED visits annually	Operationalized QI Kaizen; “everyday lean ideas” Leadership rounds Daily huddles	<p>Improved staff satisfaction to 75%</p> <p>Reduced turnover to 2%</p> <p>Anecdotal joy in work</p> <p>Standard work focus</p>	<p>Conclusion: staff engagement as key, pride in the many ideas staff had to improve</p> <p>Limitations: descriptive study, small sample</p> <p>Notes: QI training using lean methodology which focuses on front line staff engagement in QI</p>
(Bethune et al., 2016) Region wide QI training for interns in England	Pre/post survey questionnaire post 9 month training in QI Variables included attitudes and self-reported skills	First year MDs enrolled in 9 month QI training England 8 hospital region n = 93 pre & n = 80 post	18 question survey developed internally Three areas: attitudes, self-reported skill enhancement and their comfort in addressing safety concerns. Internal consistency r = 0.74 for	<p>33% response rate pre course and 28% post course</p> <p>Post course improvement in skills, but no improvement in control, (59% to 75%)</p>	<p>Conclusion: Though MDs identify QI as important, they lack skills</p> <p>Limitations: small control, low response</p> <p>Notes: <u>Curriculum info</u></p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
		Control: Small non-participating cohort also completed pre/post N = 15 pre & n = 8 post	first 2 and r = .47 for last area Likert scale	Used Kirkpatrick framework for evaluation level 2 only assessed.	Model for Improvement, driver diagrams and process mapping with a project required over 9 months in groups of 6-10 physicians each; projects presented to hospital exec group Control group analyzed, though significantly smaller group
(Hummel, 2016) Dissertation on effectiveness of QI training in the VA	Qualitative single site	10 randomly selected staff (nurses, MDs, dietary, business office) in single site VA post training	14 open ended questions; How did training affect day-to-day business Did learning lead to building capacity:	Selective coding with themes; improved efficiency, staff engagement; employee buy-in; skill building	Conclusion: QI training effective Limitations: Single site VA Notes: Curriculum info: VA's developed lean + six sigma using DMAIC approach Note: participants reflected on skill building and problem solving skills that were a by-product of training
(Eid & Quinn, 2017)	Descriptive and qualitative assessment	"Large hospital" in US between 2005 and 2014	On line survey to assess level of training	Trainee characteristics predictive of success =	Conclusion: First study to identify predictive

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Prediction of training transfer	<p>of training post QI education</p> <p>Success model bifurcates trainees into high/low training transfer then assesses characteristics related to the individual, the course and the work environment</p>	<p>n = 142 physicians who had attended QI training course between 2005 and 2014</p> <p>Interviews n = 17 (8 high scores and 11 low scores of transfer)</p>	transfer- developed internally	<p>“positive attitude toward change, motivation, mental processing skills, interpersonal skills and 6 personality characteristics (curiosity, humility, conscientiousness, resilience, wisdom and positivity”p.4</p> <p>Training course themes = project, team learning and lectures with culture, relationships and resources as sub themes (work environment)</p>	<p>factors for knowledge transfer; selecting appropriate candidates will help build capacity; attention to work environment and the course predicts success</p> <p>First study to use predictive elements for success.</p> <p>Limitations: Limited study</p> <p>Note: Curriculum info: 8 full days over 6 months, trainees work in teams of 2; QI project completed as part of program; content includes measures, variations, outcomes and organizational learning thru sharing best practices</p> <p>Can use these themes as evidence-based element</p> <p>Notes: some questions may be useful for qualitative analysis of QAP</p>

Notes: AHRQ = Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality DMAIC = Define, measure, assess, implement, control, EBP = Evidence-based Practice, HCUP = Healthcare Cost and Utilization Project FOKUS = PCMH = Patient Centered Medical Home, QSEN = Quality and Safety Education for Nurses, QAP = Quality Academy Program, TIDES = Translating Initiatives for Depression into effective Solutions,

Table A4

Table of Evidence for Curriculum Elements

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Holmboe et al., 2005) Test of curriculum design for internal medicine program	Observational prospective trial Curriculum design Outcome = improved diabetic care	13 second year Yale University internal medicine residents Control: 3 rd year residents matched pairs in continuity clinic rotations	Curriculum = improved care? Commitment to change (CTC) questionnaire completion Measured change in A1C, change in LDL, pneumovax & foot care	Intervention group patients received care consistent with QI standards, not statistically significant	Conclusions: Generalized curriculum led to improvements in patient outcomes Limitations: curriculum alone doesn't improve QI knowledge and care Notes: <u>Curriculum info:</u> 4 week didactic; required reading of IOM reports, reflection and discussion with faculty, audit and feedback
(Sockalingam et al., 2010) To develop a formal curriculum for psych residents	Descriptive study on attitudes of residents on QI training Focus groups/grounded theory	40 residents University of Toronto	Participation in QI project, perceptions of QI content,	Projects evaluated with specific criteria Barriers included workload and time to do the project Lack of integration of QI into regular curriculum	Conclusions: Iterative curriculum informed by participants is a good model Limitations small study Note: <u>Curriculum info</u> QI workshop – 8 half day sessions in 2 years

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					during 2 nd year residency Content received but application lacking
(Clegg et al., 2010) Identified critical success factors for QI training	Descriptive survey of academics and practitioners Delphi process to identify most important success factors	UK QI workshop Service & Manufacturing setting	Success factors compiled from Feignbaums 19 steps, Ishikawa's 11 points Deming's 14 points Crosby's 14 steps Juran's 10 steps	Most important QI step: Understanding root cause; Build quality into process; Constantly improve; line staff involved; use tools; use data	Conclusion: Uniquely focused on QI tools rather than overall training model Limitations: descriptive Note: a critical mass of employees must know how to use QI tools; Identified ranking of tools for understanding
(Czabanowska et al., 2012) Develop QI competence for residents in Europe	Descriptive study to identify what competencies to include in curriculum for QI for residents	Delphi process of review of literature European Association for Quality in General Practice (EQuiP)	Domains included Patient safety, ethical practice, effectiveness and efficiency, methods and tools, continuing professional development, leadership and management.	55 competencies across the 6 domains identified Competencies included managing, understanding, using different items in each domain	Conclusion: Use of a tool to determine training needs a priori Limitation: Limited Note: Model provides framework for ensuring curriculum is balanced and complete.
(Schattenkirk, 2012) Curriculum for rapid QI expansion	Peer reviewed article on lean six sigma training model	Canadian Health System	Rapidly growing capacity with curriculum focused on teaching core concepts	Ensure fit by project selection, train improvement advisors and	Conclusion: Provides a model for building curriculum

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Capacity building			to many internal employees	mentors to lead, teach through a project	Limitations: Not a study Note: Curriculum info: 2 day didactic followed by 2 week measurement; then 2 day didactic and 2 week measurement Model designed to build infrastructure for QI
(Cornett et al., 2012) Development of a standardized curriculum in public health	Descriptive study Pre/post evaluation of participant satisfaction and capacity of health departments to conduct QI Variables: PHQI101 (training program) Outcomes = increased use of QI	North Carolina public health 8 local health departments participated 26% had prior QI experience	Pre-work Training; self-report Project completion	91% could apply content; 84% could demonstrate use of tools Increased confidence by 22% to conduct QI 8 teams completed 8 projects, 7 of which had improved performance Built capacity by sharing QI tools and knowledge with an average of 9 co-workers Generated a wait list for this program	Conclusion: QI training/tools can be applied to public health Limitations: Training requires resources, small sample Curriculum info: Combined IHI MFI, lean and change management/ 6 months with a project 2 month pre-work, 2 day face to face, 4 month action period, 2 day face to face, with coaching throughout

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					<p>Leadership support critical, faculty had varied experience</p> <p>Kotter's change theory</p>
<p>(Joly, Booth, Mittal, et al., 2012)</p> <p>Development of an instrument to measure QI maturity</p>	<p>Descriptive study describing development of a QI maturity tool</p>	<p>1,161 local health departments in 16 states; psychometric testing on a maturity tool</p>	<p>Identified 4 Quality Domains: organizational culture, capacity and competency, QI practice, and alignment and spread</p>	<p>60% response rate Cronbach's on capacity and competency .89; culture .81; alignment and spread = .87, dimensions .67;</p> <p>Org culture: leadership support, staff lead, transparency with data, QI required in job duties; customer satisfaction focus, staff authority for change, sufficient resources</p> <p>QI capacity and capability: Leaders trained, staff have skills, objective measures adopted, continuous improvement model, QI prioritized</p>	<p>Conclusion: Tool needs more refinement, but dimensions measured can inform the evidence-based practices for culture, capacity and training.</p> <p>Limitations: measuring QI still early</p> <p>Notes: Tool informs elements for capacity/capability</p>
<p>(Sellers et al., 2013)</p> <p>Surgical resident QI curriculum</p>	<p>Descriptive</p> <p>1 year to complete project</p>	<p>N = 17 surgical residents PGY3</p>	<p>Survey on satisfaction with program and confidence to complete QI in the future</p>	<p>57% completed all DMAIC components; 7 projects completed; 70% confidence to conduct QI and 65% valued experience</p>	<p>Conclusion: Hands on program facilitates learning</p> <p>Limitations: Positive results linked to strong</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					<p>organization support/resources</p> <p>Note: Curriculum info: 8 hour didactic using DMAIC framework with required project using components of DMAIC</p>
(Stille et al., 2012) Quality Scholars program to build capacity	Pre/Post evaluation	10 scholars from primary care	Knowledge based pre/post eval; evaluation of each learning session; post program evaluation	Small increase in QI knowledge 31.5 to 36 not statistically significant; great increase in self-perceived readiness to conduct QI 8 of 10 scholars self-reported plan to continue QI	<p>Conclusion: Program successful, and sustained</p> <p>Limitations: 1 study site</p> <p>Note: Curriculum info 9-month program; 20 sessions; project required; experienced mentors; IHI modules; pre-work included reading list</p> <p>Note: Common theme of time to complete project; mentors critical</p>
(Wong et al., 2013)	Curriculum design	Year 3 residents 14 residents	QI projects aligns with organization, Used	85% of residents and 83% faculty completed self-	Authors' concluded faculty needed more

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Use of a curriculum that allowed for teaching and learning by residents and faculty	Residents and faculty attend together	6 faculty University of Toronto Dept. of Medicine Toronto Canada	Kirkpatrick framework for outcomes Faculty and residents work in teams on QI project	report survey “strongly agreed” that training provided necessary tools for QI	training to take on a mentorship role Limitations: small pilot, non-validated instrument Note: <u>Curriculum info</u> 2 half day classes, team project and end of academic year presentations’; surveys not tested for reliability, single site pilot 1 year course, QI intro, process mapping, team projects, rapid cycle changes,
(Brownlee et al., 2013) QI training course curriculum	Descriptive study Variables: Course ratings, Continued work on QI	University of Pittsburg Medical Center Invited operational leaders (could influence teams, had vision, director level)	Experiential and didactics To teach concepts: Red bead game Lean LEGOs® Statapult tool	62% rated class 4 of 5 50 projects completed 66% continued to work on project after course; 72% used skills learned on additional projects	Conclusion: QI diffusion across org increases success Limitations: Small study <u>Curriculum info</u> 5 4 hr. classes with webinars in between, detailed information on

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					<p>curriculum included in article; Prework reading Kotter's leading change and Berwick's User's manual for the Quality Chasm</p> <p>Note: Good info for modifying QAP, communication plan and project evaluation</p>
(Majka et al., 2013) Team based curriculum	<p>pre/post evaluation of curriculum</p> <p>Silver Module domains: QI tools; QI methods; QI facilitation; application of tools</p>	62 physicians and allied health staff in Division of Medicine at Mayo clinic	Scores on tests pre/post silver module completion	53% completed all 4 modules Pretest = 71% Posttest = 92%	<p>Conclusion: QI modules are effective</p> <p>Limitations: single site, 1 pre/post evaluation</p> <p>Curriculum info: 4 modules, pre-work on terminology; 4 modules in 1 month</p> <p>Note: modules allow for self-learning – no measure of application through a project completion</p>
(Maski et al., 2014)	Pre/post survey of comfort with QI	N = 11-14 residents in pediatric neurology program	Self-reported comfort and knowledge	Increased knowledge on how to make changes,	Conclusion: Curriculum good for residents

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Resident QI curriculum pediatric neurology	Developing aims Identifying measures Using RCA Data planning & analysis Collaboration Didactic and experiential	Harvard, Boston MA		Improved knowledge of use of tools, aims and measures, 6 resident QI projects completed 73% satisfied with course.	Limitation: responses not paired, used only process measures Note: <u>Curriculum info</u> Based on IHI open school; 3 1 hr. lectures mentor meetings, Didactic and experiential components key
(Gupta et al., 2014) Resident QI curriculum neonatology	Descriptive study Is QI essential, I understand QI Didactic & experiential portions improved ability to conduct QI QI workshops, IHI modules and unit based activities were valuable	Harvard Neonatology fellows N = 12	Self-reported measures of understanding on self-develop survey and completed knowledge assessment tool	Identifies commonalities in training; e.g. knowledge improves, didactic/experiential training most effective; team projects; longitudinal training and barriers of time, interest, available faculty and block rotations. Project completed-2 QI important and they understood	Conclusion: Content now part of core curriculum Limitations: Only 1 site, small sample Note: <u>Curriculum info</u> IHI Modules, assigned mentor, QI project assigned 2 nd year, completed 3 rd year Three workshops-overview, tools, data IHI thematic modules Authors' concluded repeated knowledge assessments would have

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					been helpful, integration into core fellowship curriculum worked well. Inconsistent application of QI tools may be due to lack of faculty experts
(Fok & Wong, 2014) QI curriculum for internal medicine	Prospective cohort study over 4 years Pre/post curriculum comparison Canadian program Self-report of confidents in making changes QI skills attainment Objective QIKAT scores Completion of QI abstract/project	University of British Columbia Internal Medicine residency 175 residents	Satisfaction index = weighted mean of group scores QIKAT validated tool to measure QI knowledge specific to internal medicine (pretest and post test versions) Confidence by self-developed survey	Satisfaction index calculated for groups = 56.4 to 69.2% QIKAT used to measure knowledge = 8.3 to 15 Confident increased to 86.6% Project evaluation criteria by experts 100% implemented Barriers included adequate time to teach and experts to teach and balancing workload with other interests.	Conclusion: Objective and subjective measures improved Limitations: High attrition, poor validity of QIKAT Note: <u>Curriculum info</u> 2 half days 4 weeks apart, 5 one hour sessions during a 12 month period, faculty mentor supervision Project teams included residents and master's level nursing students
(Williams et al., 2016) QI training to improve stroke measures	Cluster randomized QI trial IV: QI training plus feedback; vs. feedback alone	VA hospitals Intervention site: 1147 admissions Control site: 1017 admissions	Stroke measures: DVT prophylaxis, dysphasia	Improved DVT screening initially, but not sustained; no change in dysphasia screening	Conclusions: Training not sustained – contextual?

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
	DV: DVT prophylaxis & dysphasia screening				<p>Limitations: Limited to VHA hospitals,</p> <p>Note: No info on training provided other than six sigma approach; lack of sustainability probably related to lack of standard work implementation</p>
(Hall Barber et al., 2015) QI curriculum for residents	Peer reviewed article	Academic medicine program in Canada	Core roles of communicator, leader, scholar and medical expert	<p>Provides longitudinal preparation to lead QI</p> <p>Heavy focus on teams, planning, problem solving which are all translatable skills for QI work – rather than focus on QI methodology</p>	<p>Conclusion: Unique program focusing on understanding quality problems and then applying tools</p> <p>Limitations: One site</p> <p>Note: Curriculum info: Scaled program over 3 years; project focused teams; narrow focus</p>
(Ramar et al., 2015) Flipped classroom model	Quasi-experimental Pre/post evaluation of test results	N = 7 trainees Variables: trainee satisfaction, knowledge and skills acquired post sessions	Flipped classroom applies content prior to class then class time used to answer questions	Overall improvement from pre/post was 40%; strongly agreed with model, 55% agreed flipped model will increase confidence and 71% felt coaches were effective	<p>Conclusion: A flipped classroom allows for more practice time in QI work</p> <p>Limitations: small study</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
		"Silver" test		Kirkpatrick validated model	<p>Note: Curriculum Info 29 videos -135 minutes as pre-work, one half day session, workshop with tool practice</p> <p>Authors plan to continue using flipped classroom for training</p>
<p>(McNamara et al., 2016)</p> <p>Interdisciplinary training</p>	<p>Descriptive study QI Collaborative</p> <p>Improvement project impact Attendee satisfaction</p>	<p>Beaumont hospital (public teaching university hospital) in Ireland</p> <p>N = 18-35</p>	<p>Increased QI activity,</p>	<p>Workshops 8.4/10 Project reports 8.8/10</p> <p>3 fold increase in QI</p>	<p>Conclusion: Multi-modal format, allowed for more frequent tests of change</p> <p>Limitations: small sample; did not assess acquired QI knowledge</p> <p>Note: Curriculum info Voluntary lunchtime sessions 30 minutes long, initial 8 sessions on QI theory, introductory tools, PDSA cycles, etc. 35 sessions over ~1yr</p> <p>Lessons learned-mentors helped keep QI going</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Davis et al., 2016) QI Curriculum in North Carolina Public Health	Mixed methods evaluation of the PHQI 101 training program Intervention: 8 month experiential learning in QI Satisfaction scores	N = 202 37 N. Carolina public health departments	Post training project completion/sustainment New projects started post training Kirkpatrick's levels 1 (participation survey), 2 (pretest/posttest on confidence and, 3 (projects and use of tools) assessed	74% response rate, 93-98% positive for level 1, confidence post training 44-71% statistically significant at 1 month post training; project examples showed improvement and 60% participants reported sharing tools to 7 or more co-workers	Conclusion: Training successful; Leadership key; recruit early adopters, use QI advisors Limitation: One site; self-reported data Note: <u>Curriculum Info</u> Webinars and 2 face to face workshops, 4 day Kaizen with expert

Notes: ASQ-American Society for Quality CTC = Commitment to change, EQuiP = European Association for Quality in General Practice, IOM = Institute of Medicine, IHI = Institute for Healthcare Improvement, MFI = Model for Improvement, PHQ101 = Public Health QI 101, PGY3 = Post graduate year 3, QI = Quality Improvement, QIKAT = Quality Improvement Knowledge Assessment Tool, UK = United Kingdom,

Table A5

Table of Evidence Systematic Reviews

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Boonyasai et al., 2007) Systematic Review on effects of curriculum to outcomes	Systematic Review Variables: QI curriculum	39 studies; 31 team based projects; 37 didactic and experiential; pre/post and randomized	Curriculum context Learner characteristics Education strategies Evaluation methods Results Content based on IHI QI domains; customer; healthcare system; change; collaboration; new knowledge; accountability & professional knowledge	Variety of curriculum; collaboratives; Variety of teach strategies improves knowledge Only 2 studies used validated tests for change in knowledge (QIKAT)	Conclusion: Most applied adult learning, now does the learning lead to improved patient care? Limitations: publication bias recognized; recommended better focus on IHI domains Note: 2007 study so most articles older than 10 years
(Wong et al., 2010) Curriculum for med students and residents	Systematic review	NA	Learner factors for success: enthusiasm & time Teacher factors: enthusiasm and time; enough teachers Curriculum factors: didactic, experiential, longitudinal Learning environment: culture & leadership, access to data	Most measured improved knowledge and project success Most attained up to level2 of Kirkpatrick model	Conclusion: Does knowledge lead to improved outcomes? Limitations: Heterogeneity, weak designs, single centers, small numbers Curriculum info: content included QI , RCA and systems thinking; process mapping; human

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					factors; safety culture; didactic, experiential, Success hinged on enough faculty and time
(Geisz, 2013) Robert Wood Johnson study on QI training	Descriptive grant study Variables: Past QI training Current QI training All QI training	10 clinical sites across US receiving Ryan White funding for HIV Cincinnati Children's model; Boston University (Kaminski) Emory (Rask) Perfecting Patient Care (Morganti) Chapel Hill (Davis)	Goals: identify types of training, effectiveness, and contextual factors influencing knowledge transfer	Themes: Curriculum shapes training Opportunity to apply skills Organizational culture that values QI Mixed methods approach to evaluation	Conclusion: Identified common themes Limitations: Not analytical study Note: Provides an overview of several programs, best in class for QI training
(Wright & McSherry, 2013) Focused on Releasing time to care (RTC) Productive Ward	Systematic review RTC designed after Lean system	18 studies post implementation	Across studies: Patient & Staff experience Direct patient care Patient safety Financial Sustainability Exec support Barriers Success factors	Across Studies: Increased staff/patient satisfaction More direct care time Improved safety Increased ROI Sustainability growing Support essential	Conclusion: RTC has been successful, but program still new Limitations: Positive results, may be publication bias; limited objective data Note: RTC curriculum in modules similar to lean designed to build QI skills for front line staff

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
					Recommendation: embed lean into fabric of organization
(Mery et al., 2015) Systematic review of QI training	Synthesis of the literature	47 studies	Assessed: QI training QI activities Individual & organizational enables/barriers and impact	Evidence-based components identified as: QI projects included Mentoring e-learning modules Training partnerships Training in residencies Opportunities to use skills Informal coaching Patient/Community involvement QI Skills & knowledge Motivation Organizational Culture Teamwork Accountability Monitoring Impact on outcomes	Conclusion: Provides broad findings, good synthesis Limitation: No assessment for publication bias, no consort guidelines Note: Many articles retrieved and included in this TOE (last 10 years) Informs on evidence-based elements
(Mochan & Nash, 2015) Annotated Bib on QI training	Annotated Bibliography	30 references on QI training	Themes	Evidence-based components: Longitudinal project Safety Culture Patient & Family engagement Systems knowledge Teamwork Inter-organizational sharing Faculty mentors/experts Evidence-based theory	Conclusion: Identifies status of literature for resident QI training; training should begin early in medical career Limitations: Annotated bib, not a study Note: Very specific to resident training

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
(Starr et al., 2016) Systematic review of QI education	Systematic Review	QI education with clinical measures searched	IHI domains used to inform curriculum; health care system, variation & measurement; VOC, change, collaboration, social accountability, developing new knowledge, professional experts QIKAT and evaluation of projects	99 studies, 11% randomized, 53% clinical measures, 85% from US, 49% targeted inter-professionals learners, 80% required QI project, 65% included coaching.	<p>Conclusion: Most studies assessed knowledge transfer & early skills, need more studies to address outcomes</p> <p>Limitations: Published studies poorly describe curriculum</p> <p>Note: Curriculum info QI Tools, QI models (e.g. collaboratives), teaching methods didactic and experiential, Projects required and coaching/mentors provided, 22% assessed Kirkpatrick level 4b.</p> <p>Identified a decrease in coaching post 2010 – likely due to resource constraints</p>
(Mery et al., 2017) Can QI training build capacity?	Systematic review	System level evaluation of capacity	Thematic analysis 4 themes: QI training, QI activity, Individual capacity, Organizational capacity	48 articles; no system level capacity articles; 5 dimensions: QI training, QI activity, individual	Conclusion: No good measures to assess capacity – ROI important and used in other industries – we

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s) Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' conclusions; Limitations; Notes
				<p>capacity, organizational capacity and impact</p> <p>Measures of ROI most important given resources needed for training</p> <p>QI training elements: projects, coaching, training undergrads or residents, partnerships</p> <p>QI activity: skill application, informal training/coaching, patient involvement</p> <p>Individual elements: Skills, motivation & interest, individual barriers</p> <p>Organizational: culture, teams, accountability, diffusion, strategy, outcomes</p>	<p>need to use it in healthcare</p> <p>Limitations: publication bias is possible</p> <p>Note: Most source articles included in TOE</p>

Note: IHI = Institute for Healthcare Improvement, QI = Quality Improvement, QIKAT = Quality Improvement Knowledge Assessment Tool, RTC = releasing time to care, ROI = return on investment, TOE = table of evidence

APPENDIX B

PRE, POST, AND SIX-MONTH POST SURVEY QUESTIONS

Quality Academy Pre-Survey																																			
<p>* 1. What is your name?</p> <input style="width: 100%; height: 20px;" type="text"/>																																			
<p>* 2. What department do you work in?</p> <input style="width: 100%; height: 20px;" type="text"/>																																			
<p>* 3. What is your professional designation</p> <input style="width: 100%; height: 20px;" type="text"/>																																			
<p>* 4. How many years have you been in your profession?</p> <p> <input type="radio"/> 0-5 <input type="radio"/> 6-10 <input type="radio"/> 11-15 <input type="radio"/> 16-20 <input type="radio"/> >20 </p>																																			
<p>* 5. Have you had any prior experience with performance improvement?</p> <input style="width: 50px; height: 20px;" type="text"/>																																			
<p>6. If you have had prior experience, how would you describe it? (check all that apply)</p> <input style="width: 100%; height: 20px;" type="text"/>																																			
<p>* 7. Identify your level of proficiency in understanding the following: (0=not confident; 5=extremely confident</p> <table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 30%;"></th> <th style="width: 15%;">Not at all proficient</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Somewhat proficient</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Proficient</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Very Proficient</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Extremely Proficient</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr style="background-color: #cccccc;"> <td>7 A. Lean</td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="radio"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>7 B. Six Sigma</td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="radio"/></td> </tr> <tr style="background-color: #cccccc;"> <td>7 C. Model for Improvement</td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="radio"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>7 D. PDSA (Plan-do-study-act)</td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="radio"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Not at all proficient	Somewhat proficient	Proficient	Very Proficient	Extremely Proficient	7 A. Lean	<input type="radio"/>	7 B. Six Sigma	<input type="radio"/>	7 C. Model for Improvement	<input type="radio"/>	7 D. PDSA (Plan-do-study-act)	<input type="radio"/>																
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7 B. Six Sigma	<input type="radio"/>																																		
7 C. Model for Improvement	<input type="radio"/>																																		
7 D. PDSA (Plan-do-study-act)	<input type="radio"/>																																		

* 8. Identify your level of proficiency in using the following Quality Improvement Tools (0=not at all proficient; 5=extremely proficient)

	Not at all proficient	Somewhat proficient	Proficient	Very proficient	Extremely proficient
8 A. 5 Whys	<input type="radio"/>				
8 B. Value Stream Mapping	<input type="radio"/>				
8 C. Creating a Project Charter	<input type="radio"/>				
8 D. Completing a PI Template	<input type="radio"/>				
8 E. Conducting PDCA cycles	<input type="radio"/>				
8 F. Completing an A3	<input type="radio"/>				
8 G. Process flow mapping	<input type="radio"/>				
8 H. Conducting a Waste Walk	<input type="radio"/>				
8 I. 5S	<input type="radio"/>				
8 J. Driver Diagrams	<input type="radio"/>				
8 K. Benchmark Data	<input type="radio"/>				
8 L. ORCHID Reports	<input type="radio"/>				
8 M. Fishbone Diagrams	<input type="radio"/>				

* 9. Identify your level of proficiency in using the following analytical and statistical tools: (0=not at all proficient; 5= extremely proficient)

	Not at all proficient	Somewhat proficient	Proficient	Very proficient	Extremely proficient
9 A. Statistical process control charts (C-charts, P Charts, X-MR Charts)	<input type="radio"/>				
9 B. Pareto Charts	<input type="radio"/>				
9 C. Scatter plots	<input type="radio"/>				
9 D. Frequency distributions	<input type="radio"/>				
9 E. Run charts	<input type="radio"/>				

* 10. Identify your level of proficiency in the following: (0=not at all proficient; 5=extremely proficient)

	Not at all proficient	Somewhat proficient	Proficient	Very proficient	Extremely proficient
10 A. Defining the problem statement, goals and scope of a project	<input type="radio"/>				
10 B. Aligning projects to the mission, values, strategic and business priorities	<input type="radio"/>				
10 C. Managing a project to ensure the project meets milestones and goals	<input type="radio"/>				
10 D. Tracking, monitoring, and communicating project progress to all stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>				
10 E. Managing a team	<input type="radio"/>				

* 11. Identify your level of proficiency in the following: (0=not at all proficient; 5=extremely proficient)

	Not at all proficient	Somewhat proficient	Proficient	Very proficient	Extremely proficient
11 A. Promoting a culture of continuous improvement	<input type="radio"/>				
11 B. Communicating vision, expectations and PI project clearly and consistently to stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>				
11 C. Identifying barriers that impede change	<input type="radio"/>				
11 D. Improvement sustainability measures to achieve and sustain improvement	<input type="radio"/>				
11 E. Providing education, training and tools for effective implementation process and workflow changes	<input type="radio"/>				
11 F. Leading a performance improvement team	<input type="radio"/>				

Quality Academy Program Post-Survey

* 1. What is your name?

* 2. What department do you work in?

* 3. Identify your level of proficiency in understanding the following after having been in the Quality Academy.

	Not at all proficient	Somewhat proficient	Proficient	Very Proficient	Extremely Proficient
3 A. Lean	<input type="radio"/>				
3 B. Six Sigma	<input type="radio"/>				
3 C. Model for Improvement	<input type="radio"/>				
3 D. PDSA (Plan-do-study-act)	<input type="radio"/>				

* 4. Identify your level of proficiency in using the following Quality Improvement Tools after having been in the Quality Academy.

	Not at all proficient	Somewhat proficient	Proficient	Very proficient	Extremely proficient
4 A. 5 Whys	<input type="radio"/>				
4 B. Value Stream Mapping	<input type="radio"/>				
4 C. Creating a Project Charter	<input type="radio"/>				
4 D. Completing a PI Template	<input type="radio"/>				
4 E. Conducting PDSA cycles	<input type="radio"/>				
4 F. Completing an A3	<input type="radio"/>				
4 G. Process flow mapping	<input type="radio"/>				
4 I. 5S (Reducing Waste)	<input type="radio"/>				
4 J. Driver Diagrams	<input type="radio"/>				
4 K. Benchmark Data	<input type="radio"/>				
4 L. ORCHID Reports	<input type="radio"/>				
4 M. Fishbone Diagrams	<input type="radio"/>				

* 5. Identify your level of proficiency in using the following analytical and statistical tools after having been in the Quality Academy.

	Not at all proficient	Somewhat proficient	Proficient	Very proficient	Extremely proficient
5 A. Statistical process control charts (C-charts, P Charts, X-MR Charts)	<input type="radio"/>				
5 B. Pareto Charts	<input type="radio"/>				
5 C. Scatter plots	<input type="radio"/>				
5 D. Frequency distributions	<input type="radio"/>				
5 E. Run charts	<input type="radio"/>				

* 6. Identify your level of proficiency in the following after having been in the Quality Academy.

	Not at all proficient	Somewhat proficient	Proficient	Very proficient	Extremely proficient
6 A. Defining the problem statement, goals and scope of a project	<input type="radio"/>				
6 B. Aligning projects to the mission, values, strategic and business priorities	<input type="radio"/>				
6 C. Managing a project to ensure the project meets milestones and goals	<input type="radio"/>				
6 D. Tracking, monitoring, and communicating project progress to all stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>				
6 E. Managing a team	<input type="radio"/>				

* 7. Identify your level of proficiency in the following after having been in the Quality Academy.

	Not at all proficient	Somewhat proficient	Proficient	Very proficient	Extremely proficient
7 A. Promoting a culture of continuous improvement	<input type="radio"/>				
7 B. Communicating vision, expectations and PI project clearly and consistently to stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>				
7 C. Identifying barriers that impede change	<input type="radio"/>				
7 D. Improvement sustainability measures to achieve and sustain improvement	<input type="radio"/>				
7 E. Providing education, training and tools for effective implementation process and workflow changes	<input type="radio"/>				
7 F. Leading a performance improvement team	<input type="radio"/>				

* 8. How confident are you to start a new PI project?

- Very confident
 Somewhat confident
 Not confident

* 9. Name something you have learned from the Quality Academy Program and how you have incorporated it into your daily activities.

* 10. How much time were you able to allocate to your PI project?

- Less than 1 hour/week
 1-2 hours/week
 2-3 hours/week
 3+ hours/week

* 11. Have you met your goal? Why or why not?

* 12. Were you successful in the process improvements you initiated in your department? Why or why not?

* 13. How do we know that the results can be attributed to the changes made?

* 14. How can you sustain the success?

15. We value your feedback, is there anything else you would like to share with us?

Quality Academy Program: 6-month Follow Up Survey

* 1. What is your name?

* 2. What department do you currently work in?

* 3. Is this a change from when you were in the Quality Academy Program?

- No
 Yes

4. If yes, was this change a result of a promotion?

- Yes
 No

* 5. What is your professional designation?

Other (please specify)

* 6. Please indicate the current status of your Quality Academy Program Project

- Complete and transitioned as a sustainable part of everyday operations
 Complete, but no longer a part of everyday operations due to process changes
 Not complete, but continuing to monitor and do QI work on it
 Not complete and no longer monitored
 Other

Other (please specify)

* 7. Since completing the Quality Academy Program, have you made updates to your Project's run chart?

- Yes
 No

* 8. Since completing the Quality Academy Program, have you run any additional tests of change (PDSA) for your Project?

- Yes
 No

* 9. Did you spread your Quality Academy Program Project to other units/services within the medical center?

- No
 Yes

If yes, please comment

* 10. Since completion of the Quality Academy Program, have you participated in or led one or more QI Projects?

- Yes- participated in
 Yes - led
 Yes - participated in & led
 No

* 11. Are you interested in becoming a QI mentor?

Note: To become a mentor you must have led 3 or more QI projects post the Quality Academy Program

- No
 Yes

* 12. Since the completion of the Quality Academy Program, have you furthered your education in QI?

- No
 Yes

If yes, please explain.

* 13. Have you attended any of the Quality Toolbox Workshops?

- Yes
- No
- No, when are the classes?
Look here - http://myladhs.lacounty.gov/lacusc/depts/QI/SitePages/QI_Training.aspx

* 14. Have you used the Quality Improvement Website in the past 6 months? If so, how often?

- 1 time per month
- 2-5 times per month
- >5 times per month
- No
- No, show me where it is
Click Here - <http://myladhs.lacounty.gov/lacusc/depts/QI/SitePages/Home.aspx>

15. Any other comments?

APPENDIX C

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD (HOSPITAL AND UNIVERSITY)

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects

P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7449 / F 657-278-7258

APPROVAL NOTICE

From the Institutional Review Board
California State University Fullerton

Date: **August 2, 2017**

From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board

To: **Laura Saifl**
Department: School of Nursing

Re: Use of Human Subjects in Research Project entitled:
Building Capacity and Capability to Sustain Quality Initiatives: Evaluating a Quality Academy Program

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human subjects in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University Fullerton, Institutional Review Board ("CSUF IRB"). Your proposal is determined to be Exempt per 45 CFR § 46.101(b)(4).

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

If the above-referenced project has not been completed by **August 1, 2018** you must request renewed approval for continuation of the proposal.

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participation and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires resubmission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation. Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-referenced title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any change in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chairman of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that s/he is responsible for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

This Institution has an Assurance on file with the Office for Human Research Protections.
The Assurance Number is FWA00015354.

Cc: Dr. Penny Weismuller
Application No. HSR-17-0335

Proposal #HS-17-00413

University of Southern California Health Sciences Campus
 Institutional Review Board
 LAC+USC Medical Center, General Hospital Suite 4700
 1200 North State Street, Los Angeles, CA 90033
 (323) 223-2340 phone
 (323) 224-8389 fax
irb@usc.edu

Date: Jun 05, 2017, 02:35pm
 To: [Laura Sarff, RN](#)
 Interim Chief Operating Officer
 LAC + USC Medical Center

From: Health Sciences Institutional Review Board

TITLE OF PROPOSAL:
 Building capacity and capability to sustain quality initiatives:
 Evaluating a Quality Academy Program ([QAP Evaluation](#))

Action 6/5/2017 Action Approve
 Date: Taken:

Comm Institutional Review Board
 ittee:

Note: Your iStar application and attachments were reviewed
 by the IRB on June 5, 2017.

The project was APPROVED.

The materials submitted and considered for review of this project included:

1. iStar application dated 5/26/17
2. Study protocol, uploaded on iStar 5/26/17

Based on the information submitted for review, this study is exempt from 45 CFR 46 according to §46.101(b) as category 1.

As research which is considered exempt according to §46.101(b), this project is not subject to requirements for continuing review. You are authorized to conduct this research as approved. The project has been entered in the iStar database. *Please notify the IRB of any significant changes that may alter the Exempt status of this research activity.*

The HIPAA Privacy Rule will not apply to this research. The investigator certifies that he/she is not accessing, using or obtaining protected (i.e., identifiable) health information held by: a) a health care provider (e.g., physician or other health care practitioner, hospital, clinic, nursing home); b) health plan (e.g., group health plan, insurance company, (HMO)); or c) health care clearinghouse (e.g., billing service) that is governed by the HIPAA privacy federal regulations.

Attachments:

D. Hospital Permission to Use Surveys

Los Angeles County
Board of Supervisors

June 13, 2017

Hilda L. Solis
First District

Mark Ridley-Thomas
Second District

Sheila Kuehl
Third District

Janice Hahn
Fourth District

Kathryn Barger
Fifth District

Bonnie Billich, RN, MSN
Interim Chief Executive Officer

Brad Spellberg, MD
Chief Medical Officer

Laura Sarff, RN, MSN
Interim Chief Operating Officer

Isabel Milan, RN
Dialysis Unit Chief

To whom it may concern:

I am the Interim Chief Quality Officer at LAC+USC and one of the faculty for the Quality Academy Program (QAP). This program has collected self-reported survey data from participants in the Quality Academy using SurveyMonkey.

I hereby give Ms. Sarff permission to obtain a spreadsheet (with identifying names removed) of completed surveys for all QAP waves and redacted copies of any other completed survey data to use in her Doctor of Nursing program project.

Should you have any questions, please feel free to contact me at (323) 409-6535.

1200 N. State Street
Inpatient Tower (IPT)
2nd Floor, Room 2B1100
Los Angeles, CA 90033

Tel: (323) 409-2800
Fax: (323) 441-8038

Eric K. Wei, MD, MBA
Interim Chief Quality Officer

To ensure access to high-quality, patient-centered, cost-effective health care to Los Angeles County residents through direct services at DHS facilities and through collaboration with community and university partners.

Health Services
www.dhs.lacounty.gov

APPENDIX E

SUMMARY OF CURRICULUM CHANGES BETWEEN WAVES

Course	Wave 1	Wave 2	Wave 3
Generic Changes		Required attendance for all workshops	Required participant get 25% reduction of duties to ensure project completion
Performance Improvement (PI) Basics	Session 1	Session 1	Session 1
Team Dynamics	Session 1	Session 2	Session 1
Starting a PI project	Session 2	Session 1	Session 1
Completing an A3	Session 2	Session 2	Session 2
Process Mapping & Tools	Session 2	Session 3	Session 3
5 Dysfunctions of a team	Not included	Not included	Session 3
RCA & PDSA Tools	Session 3	Combined	Combined
PDSA Paper Airplane Activity	Session 3	Session 3	Session 2
Robbie the Robot Lean Simulation	Session 4	Session 6	Session 6
Fun with Data Activity	Session 5	Split into 2 parts Part 1 Session 3 Part 2 Session 5	Part 1 Session 2 Part 2 Session 5
Team Management	Session 5	Session 5	Not included
Former graduate presentations	Not included	Not included	Session 5
Project Presentations	Sessions 4, 5, 6, 7	Session 7	Sessions 2, 4, 6 In small groups (4-5) with individual faculty
5S simulation	Session 6	Session 4	Session 4
Structured Waste Walk	Session 6	Session 4	Session 4
Building Sustainability	Session 7	Session 7	Session 7
Leadership	Session 7	Session 7	Session 7
Final Project Presentations	Session 8	Session 8	Session 8

APPENDIX E
SKILLS CHECKLISTS (WAVES 2 AND 3)

**Quality Academy Program
Skills Checklist**

Name:	Mentor Name:
--------------	---------------------

Logistics

Assignment	Date of Completion	N/A	Mentor Initials	Participant Initials
Initial Mentor, Mentee, Supervisor Meeting				
Mid-program Mentor, Mentee, Supervisor Meeting				
Schedule All Mentor Meetings				
Wave 2 Quality Academy Pre-Program Survey				
Wave 2 Quality Academy Post-Program Survey				
Identify a computer with Macros				

Project Management

Assignment	Date of Completion	N/A	Mentor Initials	Participant Initials
Identify an Improvement Project				
Project Alignment with Strategic Goals				
Aim Statement				
Background & Current Condition of Problem				
Assess ROI Savings				
Build a Team for the Project				
Sustainability Plan				

Performance & Process Improvement Methods

Methods	Date of Completion	N/A	Mentor Initials	Participant Initials
PDSA				
Complete 1 st Test of Change				
Complete 2 nd + Test of Change				
Collecting Data				
Process Measure				
Balancing Measure				
Outcome Measure				

Quality Improvement Tools

Tools	Date of Completion	N/A	Mentor Initials	Participant Initials
A3				
Project Charter				
RCA				
5 Whys				
Mapping				

Information Resources

Resources	Date of Completion	N/A	Mentor Initials	Participant Initials
Literature Review / Published Research				
HER				
Online Data Bases				
Benchmark Data				

Analytical Tools

Tools	Date of Completion	N/A	Mentor Initials	Participant Initials
Control Chart				
Run Chart				
Driver Diagram				

Visual Tools

Tools	Date of Completion	N/A	Mentor Initials	Participant Initials
Graphs				
Dashboards				
Scorecards				

Supervisor Signature

Date

APPENDIX F

PROJECT TEMPLATE

Project: [this is the name of the project] Project Leader: [this is the project leader] Executive Sponsor: [this is the name of the person sponsoring the project who can assist with resources, etc] EC member Quality Improvement Project Team Members: [this is to identify the QI team members who participated in project]	
TRIPLE AIM	What are we trying to accomplish: <i>this is the project aim or goal statement</i> Why is it important for patient experience/patient safety: <i>this explains the linkage to patient safety/experience</i> Alignment with Balanced Scorecard and Quality Goals: <i>patient experience, to improve transitions, to improve patient flow, to improve publicly reported data</i>

Process Measure Chart

Control chart

This section should include the driver diagram or plan for improvement

Outcome Measure Chart

Control chart

KEY METRICS		Balancing Measure Chart
Process Measure(s)	<i>Measure the process that is being changed; linked to outcomes</i>	Control chart
Outcome Measure(s)	<i>Measures the outcome (what are we trying to accomplish)</i>	
Balancing Measure(s)	<i>Measures unintended consequences of change or changes in the system expected or not</i>	
PDSA/ACTION PLANS		Long-Term Sustainability Plan
	<i>This defines actions take or changes tested through PDSA cycles</i>	<i>This identifies plan for long term sustainability; how will this become standard operating procedure</i>

APPENDIX G
POST COURSE SURVEY

|

QUALITY ACADEMY PROGRAM

Please evaluate the instructor by using the criteria listed below and checking the appropriate box:

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Poor
Preparation (Handouts, audiovisuals, classroom, began on time)					
Class objectives (clear, covered in content)					
Outlines, handouts, syllabus (clear, and relevant to content)					
Audiovisual aids (slides, clear and relevant to content)					
Knowledge of subject (able to answer questions, elaborates on content)					
Delivery of information (clear, organized, logical frequency)					
Teaching technique (maintains student attention, relaxed, enthusiastic, elicits student participation)					
Professional attitude (facilitates student participation, deals with student's opinion)					
Overall evaluation of the program					

Comments: Your comments are appreciated and are used to improve classes.

APPENDIX H

QUALITY ACADEMY PROGRAM ADVERTISING FLYER

Provider approved by the
California Board of
Registered Nursing
Provider #10563,
21 Contact Hours
Los Angeles County College
of Nursing and Allied Health
1237 N. Mission Road, Bldg. 10
Los Angeles, CA 90033

APPLY NOW!

Check the LAC+USC
Quality Improvement webpage for
application details, deadline,
and/or contact us!

[http://myladhs.lacounty.gov/lacuscd/dep
ts/QI/SitePages/Home.aspx](http://myladhs.lacounty.gov/lacuscd/dep
ts/QI/SitePages/Home.aspx)

PROGRAM CONTACT

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Quality Academy Program

Professional Development Program

Building improvement
capacity and developing
effective leaders

Open to Physicians, Nurses &
Other Hospital Staff

Program Overview

The goal of this program is to expand the capacity for improvement at LAC+USC Medical Center by developing effective leaders in Quality Improvement who are able to accomplish improvement strategies.

The curriculum is designed to prepare health care professionals in quality improvement efforts and provide the tools to develop, implement, and sustain process improvement projects.

Participants will be asked to identify a specific project to be conducted in their respective departments and/or work areas. The participant's supervisor must authorize performance of this project in their work area.

There will be one primary faculty member who will provide 1:1 mentorship to successfully complete the performance improvement project.

Workshop Logistics

The workshops are a combination of lectures and interactive group activities.

There are (8) four-hour workshops over the course of a six-month program.

Full commitment to assigned course work, monthly reports, meetings, exercise assignments between workshops, as well as full attendance, is required.

Program Dates

Semiannual program starting in April & October.

See website for program dates.

Improvement Project

Each Quality Academy Participant will design and learn an improvement project that will provide an opportunity to apply theories and methods learned in the program.

Through teamwork and collaboration, participants will run many tests of change to implement process improvements which can be sustained.

APPENDIX I

PROJECT TEMPLATE EVALUATION DATA ABSTRACTION TOOL

Project ID	Data Abstraction Tool	YAP Projects		
		All are dichotomous (Yes/No)	yes	no
	Patient Outcome	Project aims to improve outcome		
		Is focused on the outcome		
		Includes direction of change		
	The Aim (points possible)	Includes what by when language		
		Are relevant to the aim		
		Uses existing data or data that is easily available or data can be trended		
		Captures key process or outcome (Relative to aim)		
	The Measures (points possible)	Includes appropriate balancing measure		
		Represent the data measured		
		Use type that best represents data (bar vs control run)		
	The Charts	Annotates charts with PDSA's		
		Provides sufficient detail to duplicate change		
		Includes more than one cycle		
	PDSA/Action Plans			
		Is relevant plan given the outcomes achieved		
	The Long Term Sustainability Plan	Includes change that is permanent		
		Data trend shows improvement		
	The Outcome	Project outcome goal met		
	Total Points			